

NYANSAPO COLLEGE

ILLEGAL MINING AND GHANA'S ENVIRONMENTAL SECURITY:
CASE OF CHINESE ACTIVITIES AT AWODUA

BY

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DECEMBER, 2021.

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DECLARATION

Candidate's Declaration

I hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my original work and that no part of this dissertation has been presented for another degree in this University or elsewhere.

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Supervisors' Declaration

We hereby declare that the preparation and presentation of the dissertation was supervised in accordance with the guidelines on supervision of dissertation laid down by Nyansapo College, Accra.

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ABSTRACT

This study focused essentially on analyzing China's illegal mining in Ghana and its implications for Ghana's environmental security, with specific focus to the Awodua Community of the Wassa-Amenfi District, in the Western region of Ghana. The study is purely qualitative exploratory descriptive design that relied on both primary and secondary data for analysis. The primary data was obtained through interviews from key informants who have in-depth knowledge about the topic under study, whereas secondary data was obtained through literature review from sources such as books, newspapers, journals and internet sources. One of the findings from the study revealed that China's interest in Ghana's gold resources have contributed significantly to illegal mining activities carried out by some Chinese nationals and companies in Ghana which consequently has implications for Ghana's environmental security. The study concludes that the prevalence of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana, with particular reference to the Awodua community has conspicuous implications for Ghana's environmental security. The study recommends that the Government of Ghana should ensure that its state security and environmental protection institutions should be adequately financed, well-resourced and equipped in providing quality service delivery.

KEY WORDS

Environmental Security;

Illegal Mining Activities;

China;

Ghana;

Awodua Community;

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to the Almighty God, my mother Felicia and siblings for their immense contribution, sacrifice and prayers in seeing to it that, this work becomes a reality and a success.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AU	African Union.
BNI	Bureau of National Investigations.
CNC	Computer Numeric Control.
EF	Ecological Footprint.
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States.
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment.
EJF	Environmental Justice Foundation.

EPA	Environmental Protection Agency.
EU	European Union.
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment.
FC	Forestry Commission.
FOCAC	Forum on China-Africa Cooperation.
GAF	Ghana Armed Forces.
GPS	Ghana Police Service.
ICRW	International Convention for Regulating Whaling.
MEST	Ministry of Environment, Science and Technology.
NDC	National Democratic Congress
NEPP	National Environment Protection Policy.
NEPAD	New Partnership for Africa's Development.
NPP	New Patriotic Party
PNDCL	Provisional National Defence Council Law.
UK	United Kingdom.
UN	United Nations.
UNCED	United Nations Conference on Environment and Development.
UNCHE	United Nations Conference on Human Environment.
UNDP	United Nations Development Program.
UNGA	United Nations General Assembly.
US	United States.

UHAS	University of Health and Allied Sciences.
RAIP	Regional Agriculture Investment Program.
REC	Regional Economic Community.
RIP	Regional Implementation Planning.
RPFS	Regional Program for Food Security.
SAKSS	Strategic Analysis and Knowledge Support System.
SPFS	Special Program for Food Security.
UDEAO	Union Donaiere des Etats de L’Afrique de ‘Ouest.
WAEMU	West African Economic and Monetary Union.
WAPP	West African Productivity Program.
WB	World Bank

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

The negative environmental security impacts of illegal mining by the Chinese are beginning to be felt across the African continent, with Ghana not being an exception (Bach, 2014). The practice continues to pose dire human security consequences to citizens on the continent. Illegal mining activities by some Chinese pose dire health and security threats to citizens in some African states including, respiratory health threats, land degradation, air pollution, water pollution, among others (Shinn, 2016). This qualitative exploratory case study explored the environmental security threats posed by illegal mining activities by some Chinese in Ghana with a focus on the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

This qualitative exploratory case study with a collective design, explored the views of 12 experts including officials from the Minerals Commission and Lands Commission in Ghana and the Ghana Armed Forces involved in Operation Vanguard to check illegal mining activities across the country. Findings from the qualitative exploratory case study informed recommendations for effective reversal and curbing of illegal mining activities in Ghana. The scope of chapter one consisted of background to the study, statement of the problem, the purpose of the study, research objectives, research questions, significance of the study, delimitations, limitations, and organization of the study.

Background to the Study

Challenges which confront global environmental security are significant with dire consequences to human survival (Palsson et al., 2013).

These include an exponential surge in population growth with significant demand in energy use, which has also prompted a high demand for natural resources in the face of resource scarcity. Three decades ago, movements that championed the cause of enhancing global environment security, as well as protecting the international natural environment concentrated more on issues and challenges associated with poor waste management, provision of potable safe drinking water, and air pollution (Doyle et al, 2015). From the beginning of the Millennium, scholarly attention and campaigns on global environmental security have focused on challenges associated with natural resource scarcity, land degradation, global warming and climate change, greenhouse gas emissions leading to the perpetual depletion of the ozone layer, illegal natural resource extraction among others (Hannigan, 2014).

There have as a result been ragging concerns among environmentalists and scientists on the implications of improper natural resource extraction in Africa, particularly because of how such practices continue to deplete the already weak natural cycle upon which all fauna and flora survive (Reed, 2014). Africa is considered an epicenter for natural resources in the contemporary international ecosystem due to the preponderance of natural resources in the region, and this has attracted a heightened scramble for natural resources on the continent.

After the end of the Cold War, most African states anticipated that the developed world will help initiate, propel and sustain the development of the African continent. Notwithstanding the hope of African states to receive development assistance from the advanced world, the African continent remains the poorest continent in the world amidst the preponderance of natural

resources. Africans have benefitted little from their natural resources whilst the developed states are benefitting more from the available natural resources on the continent including gold, oil, water, uranium, timber, untilled arable land, bauxite, diamond, among others (Le Billon, 2017). The situation is disturbing as resource extraction in Africa is mostly carried out in a manner that degrades the environment and thus, raises concerns about environmental security. China has shown significant interest in Africa's natural resources and as such has made several economic and financial investments in various African states to gain access to the region's natural resources.

In 2005, Sahr Johnny (Sierra Leone's Ambassador to China) noted that: The Chinese are doing more than the G8 to make poverty history. If a G8 country had wanted to rebuild the stadium, we'd still be holding meetings! The Chinese just come and do it. They don't hold meetings about environmental impact assessment, human rights, bad governance, and good governance. I'm not saying it is right, just that Chinese investment is succeeding because they don't set high benchmarks (Hilsum, 2005, pp. 1).

The increasing extraction of natural resources by the Chinese has become worrisome due to the increasing environmental degradation posed by such activities which negatively affect the quality of human life among most African populations (Abass, 2010). This situation is particularly evident in Sudan. The China National Petroleum Corporation penetrated Sudan and expanded its exploration after the withdrawal of Western competitors due to public outrage over their involvement in Sudan's civil war in 1995 (Shinn, 2016). In this regard, China made huge investments in Sudan including the

construction of the Merowe Dam, thermal and hydroelectric power plants including, an oil refinery, pipeline, and railways (Shinn, 2016). China has made similar investments in other parts of Africa including Nigeria, Angola, Ethiopia, Zambia, Congo, and Ghana. Most of China's economic investments in Africa are focused on sensitive sectors (such as oil and gas exploration, timber, hydropower, and mining). Such investments are sometimes associated with dire environmental security ramifications. This is because such investments sometimes require infrastructure projects such as the construction of roads, pipelines and railways, and roads to help facilitate the projects, which are associated with air, sound, land degradation, and pollution.

In contemporary times, China has shown significant interest in natural resource extraction in Ghana, with much concentration on gold. While this is supposed to engender the economic development of Ghana, there have been increasing concerns about how some Chinese engage in illegal mining with threats to the environment and health security consequences in designated areas. This qualitative exploratory collective case study explored the environmental security implications of illegal gold mining by some Chinese in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, of the Western region of Ghana.

Statement of the Problem

Oil is the main natural resource imported by the Chinese from Africa (Mohan & Lampert, 2013). In addition, other natural resources including cobalt, copper, iron metal, manganese, and gold have likewise been massively imported from the African continent by China (Mohan & Lampert). Consequently, China gives out significant financial assistance to African states

as a contribution towards infrastructural and economic development in exchange for such natural resources (Edoho, 2011).

The financial support from China to African states becomes a lure that most African leaders cannot reject since they need such assistance to instigate and sustain economic development in their countries. This situation has on many occasions attracted unfair, unlawful, unjustifiable, and improper extraction of natural resources by some Chinese from Africa with dire environmental security consequences.

There is a raging debate among scholars on the importance of Chinese presence and the increasing phenomenon of economic investment in Africa. Taylor (2009), for example, contended that the presence and enthusiasm of the Chinese Government in Africa in instigating and sustaining massive economic and infrastructural investments, which could have been extremely difficult or impossible for some African states to achieve on their own. Contrary to Taylor's view, (Alden, 2009), argues that most of the loans and grants provided to African states by China are not necessarily to propel development on the continent but to gain significant access and control over natural resources, which in the long run do not benefit Africans in any way.

Ghana has since the 1960s forged strong diplomatic ties with China. This relation was given a boost by the current President of the Republic of Ghana. His Excellency President Nana Addo Dankwa Akufo-Addo of Ghana remarked at the 73rd United Nations (UN) General Assembly meeting, that: "Ghana like many countries in Africa is forging relations with China to make arrangements to help address part of our infrastructure deficits," (MyJoyOnline News, 2018, p.1).

President Akufo-Addo's proclamation suggests a friendly posture of Ghana towards China. Even though there exists a cordial relationship between the two states, there is also an increasing concern in recent times regarding the nature of this relationship. The fact of the matter is that Ghana keeps on battling with ecological deterioration because of the involvement of Chinese nationals in illicit mining (galamsey), among others that contaminate water bodies notably in rural communities in Ghana. Along these lines, as much as there is by all accounts a closer tie between the two states, China's advantage and abuse of some natural resources, with specific reference to illegal mining of gold in Ghana have contributed to the environmental threats and insecurities which confront Ghana in recent times.

This qualitative exploratory case study explored environmental security implications of illegal gold mining by some Chinese in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana. This qualitative exploratory case study with a collective case study design, explored the views of 12 experts made up of officials from the Minerals Commission and Lands Commission in Ghana, the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation in Ghana, and the Ghana Armed Forces (task force involved in Operation Vanguard to check illegal mining activities across the country). The views and opinions obtained have provided first-hand insight into a greater understanding of recent environmental security threats posed by Chinese illegal mining activities in Africa, with a special focus on Ghana.

Purpose of the Study

This qualitative exploratory collective case study explored the nature and scope of Ghana-Sino relations with particular focus on the involvement of Chinese in illegal mining and its implications on environmental security in the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana. This qualitative exploratory collective case study also explored contemporary conditions and drivers that facilitate the exploitation of Ghana's gold resources, successes, as well as challenges encountered with regards to addressing illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. The purpose of the study was achieved through purposive interviews of 12 participants who have in-depth knowledge on environmental security threats posed by activities of some Chinese nationals involved in illegal mining in Africa, with a special focus on Ghana.

Research Objectives

The following research objectives were developed from the purpose statement and provided a guide to this qualitative exploratory case study:

1. To explore the contemporary conditions in Ghana-Sino relations that have facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources.
2. To explore the environmental security implications of illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals.
3. Explore the challenges which have confronted the fight against illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana.
4. To explore and propose solutions to resolve Ghana's environmental security and related threats that result from illegal mining by Chinese nationals in Ghana.

Research Questions

The following research questions have been developed from the research objectives to guide the qualitative exploratory case study:

1. How have contemporary Ghana-Sino relations facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources?
2. How have illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals influenced Ghana's environmental security?
3. Which challenges have confronted the fight against illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?
4. How can environmental security be improved with specific reference to illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?

Significance of the Study

This qualitative exploratory collective case study is timely since it was carried out in a period which attracted increased concerns by both the Government of Ghana and the Ghanaian populace about the dire environmental insecurities posed by illegal mining activities by some Chinese in Ghana. Findings from the study contributed to the larger debate on China's increasing interest in the economic development of Africa, against the increasing environmental security threats posed by illegal mining on the continent. More specifically, an intellectual exercise such as this has contributed new knowledge to the world of academia.

This qualitative exploratory study provided recommendations that could be relied upon by the Government of Ghana and other African leaders in the efficient management of natural resources notably the extraction of gold. Findings have also provided recommendations for state actors, students,

researchers, regional integration organizations such as ECOWAS and international organizations such as the UN, as well as for future research on China's illegal mining activities in Africa and its implications for environmental security to make interventions in case of African-Sino relations.

Delimitations

Ghana-China relations could be traced to the 1960s when formal diplomatic relations began between the two states. This implies that several forms of bilateral relations have ensued between the two states ranging from economic, security to development assistance. However, in the last decade, there have been increasing threats to environmental security due to the increasing phenomenon of illegal mining by some Chinese in Ghana. The scope of this qualitative exploratory study covered the period 2010-2020; a period that witnessed the increasing phenomenon of Chinese illegal mining operations in the country. This qualitative exploratory study focused on the environmental security threats posed by illegal mining activities in Ghana. The Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana, was selected as the study area for this qualitative exploratory collective study. The factors considered in this qualitative exploratory collective case study included land degradation, air pollution, sound pollution, and water pollution. Factors excluded include depletion of the ozone layer, greenhouse effect, and climate change.

Limitations

This qualitative exploratory case study utilized both primary and secondary sources of data for analysis. The researcher anticipated challenges in obtaining primary data from experts through semi-structured open-ended

interview questions as a result of the existing threat of the Coronavirus pandemic, which has limited movements and face-to-face interactions. To overcome this challenge, the researcher resorted to virtual means to obtain primary data from 12 experts. Virtual platforms such as e-mails, telephone calls, WhatsApp chats, Skype, and or Zoom meetings were used.

Organization of the Study

Documentation of this qualitative exploratory collective case study research is divided into five chapters. Chapter one contained background to the study, statement of the problem, objectives of the research, research questions, significance of the study, delimitations, limitations, definition of terms, and organization of the study. Chapter two focused on a review of related literature on related topics. These include the theoretical framework, literature search, review of seminal literature, review of recently published works on Ghana-Sino relations, and analysis of gaps in the literature. Chapter three contained the research methods used for data collection and analysis to arrive at findings. The chapter consisted of research design, study area, population, sampling procedure, data collection instruments, data collection procedures, data processing, and analysis.

Chapter four presented the results and discussions. This included data analysis and interpretation. The qualitative exploratory collective design was employed to collect and analyze data that reflect the main objective of the study, which is the implication of Chinese illegal mining on Ghana's environmental security. Chapter five contains a summary, conclusions, and recommendations of the study. These provide an overview of the entire dissertation, the purpose of the study, the research questions, and the research

methods employed. Chapter five also provided major findings of the study, conclusions derived from the findings of the study that also informed recommendations made for addressing and tackling the menace of some Chinese involvement in illegal mining activities in Ghana.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory collective case study was to explore the nature and scope of Ghana-Sino relations with a particular focus on the involvement of some Chinese in illegal mining and implications on environmental security in the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana. The purpose of the study was achieved through purposive interviews of 12 participants who have in-depth knowledge on environmental security threats posed by activities of some Chinese nationals involved in illegal mining in Africa, with a special focus on Ghana. The literature review section is categorized into five main sub-sections: (i) theoretical framework; (ii) literature search; (iii) review of seminal works on China's illegal mineral extraction in Africa; (iv) review of recently published literature on African-Sino relations; (v) gaps in the literature, and (vi) chapter summary.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework establishes the theoretical foundation under which an analysis is made in research (Denzin, 2017). A theoretical framework describes and introduces the theory which explains why the research problem under study exists. Several theories could be used to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. The theory of ecological footprint (EF) was chosen to anchor discussions of scholarly works of illegal mining and its implications on environmental security. The theory of EF was propounded by Mathis Wackernagel in 1990 but was given much prominence in academia in

1992 by William Rees (a renowned ecological economist (Peng et al, 2019)). The EF theory evaluates the demands by individuals and states on common global resources and the security ramifications such demands have on the environment.

The theory has become one of the standout theories often utilized in analyzing the impact of human activities on the natural environment, with specific reference to cultural practices, resource consumption, and utilization and sustainability of natural resources between and among states (Hayden, 2011). The theory of EF analyzes the degree to which a group of people or population utilizes available natural resources to meet the demands of an increasing population, and the impact such consumption has on the natural environment. The theory is, therefore, used to evaluate the utilization or consumption of natural resources and their associated environmental security consequences at the state, regional and international levels.

Proponents of the theory assert that the main reason for the overexploitation of natural resources due to overdependence is the demands of increasing population which requires diversification into new ventures to satisfy human wants. The main argument of the EF theory outlines that exploitation or overdependence on natural resources in a given region or state could lead to dire ecological security threats including erosion, land degradation, and extreme famine if sustainable practices are not adhered to or adopted in the utilization or extraction of natural resources (Peng et al, 2019). Therefore, the exploitation of natural resources by foreign nationals in another state which results in dire ecological security threats could attract grievances and sentiments among local citizens or inhabitants of regions where natural

resources could be found. This situation has a high tendency of instigating civil wars or conflicts.

Critics of the theory argued that developed countries with huge cities, growing middle class, and sophisticated lifestyles tend to have a correspondingly high demand for natural resources to meet their insatiable needs leading to over-consumption of resources (Miglietta & Pastore, 2010). The growing demand for such resources most often engenders illegal practices to gain access to natural resource reserves, thereby leading to degeneration or depletion in natural resources, with less sustainability for future generations (Mostafa, 2010). The theory of EF also argues that states with over-dependency or exploitation of natural resources have a deficit in terms of their carrying capacity, thereby necessitating the need to rely on resources from other states or regions to meet the demand of their increasing population (Miglietta & Pastore, 2010). Consequently, these developments also lead to the depletion of resource reserves of dependent states, which in turn reduce their ecological carrying capacity.

The theory of EF, like any other theory, is without criticism. Firstly, Homer-Dixon (2010), opines that the theory ignores technological change and does not take into consideration the use of environmentally friendly technologies. Secondly, the theory does not consider the underground resources such as resources in the ocean. The theory focuses predominantly on resources on land surfaces (Van den Bergh & Grazi, 2014). Finally, the theory offers no policy prescription other than focusing more on land use, reduction of consumption per head, and population (Ponthiere, 2009).

Notwithstanding the above criticisms, the theory is suitable for analysis in this qualitative exploratory collective case study. This is because the theory has gained wide recognition and acceptance in analyzing unsustainable consumption of natural resources through cooperation between and among states which has ramifications on the environmental security of a state, region, or entire globe. In addition, it provides useful indicators for sustainable natural resource use that is easy to communicate and understand (Peng et al, 2019). Towards this end, the theory is suitable for analyzing significant environmental or ecological impacts which arise as a result of illegal mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana, with specific reference to the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, of the Western region of Ghana.

The EF theory has become the main concept or model adopted by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development for exploring pathways toward achieving a "one-planet economy" by 2050 (Hayden, 2011). Subsequently, several states and regional integration organizations including the United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, Japan, Switzerland, Wales, and the European Union have also embraced the theory or concept (Hayden, 2011). Based on the points the theory presents, it makes it suitable for the objectives of this research study which explored the exploitation of gold resources and its implications for Ghana's environmental security and related challenges.

Literature Search

A literature search is a systematic, thorough search of all types of literature (e.g., books, peer-reviewed articles, etc. on a research topic (Rau, 2004). The researcher reviewed scholarly works on Ghana-Sino relations that

are relevant to this qualitative exploratory collective case study. Secondary data such as books, journals, and other scholarly works from both online and physical libraries were reviewed on Ghana-Sino relations for the research study. The literature search from secondary sources was facilitated by the motive to obtain relevant data which helped throw more light on the objectives of the study as well as identify gaps which this qualitative explorative case study has filled.

Review of Seminal Works on China's illegal mineral extraction in Africa

Lindlof & Taylor (2017), describe seminal works as pivotal or landmark studies, which are scholarly works, particularly, articles that initially presented an idea of great importance or influence within a particular discipline. Identifying seminal articles relies heavily on your thoroughness in the examination and synthesis of the scholarly literature concerning the objectives of a particular study. This section of this qualitative exploratory collective case study reviewed and discussed scholarly works on illegal mineral extraction in Africa by some Chinese nationals. Sub-themes discussed include: (i) China's foreign policy in Africa, (ii) Africa and China bilateral relations, (iii) China's foreign direct investments in Africa, and (iv) China and international environmental frameworks.

China's Foreign Policy towards Africa

Banchirigah (2008) explains illegal mining as the mining activity that is undertaken without proper or approved state permission, with particular reference to land rights, mining licenses, and exploration or mineral transportation permits. Banchirigah asserted that foreign aid is the wheels on which international relations thrive. Banchirigah explained that foreign aid

enhances the better and faster pursuit of foreign policies (Taylor, 2009). In this vein, China's foreign policy to Africa has been geared towards establishing friendly relations and also providing financial aid and infrastructure assistance to most African states (Banchirigah, 2008). For instance, Premier Zhou Enlai of China established the economic principles which he saw relevant to influence the foreign policy agenda of China to date (Banchirigah).

These economic principles were established to strengthen technological and economic cooperation between Africa and China (Aidoo, 2010). Paramount among China's economic principles influencing its foreign policy in Africa include achieving practical results, diversification of economies, utilization of pragmatic economic principles and practices and acceleration of economic development showed significant relevance to this qualitative explorative case study since these explained the economic principles that influence China's interest in Ghana's gold resources. This qualitative collective case study further explored pull factors that sustain the interest of the Chinese in Ghana's extractive sector and how this could be reversed.

Africa and China Bilateral Relations

To fortify bilateral relations between China and Africa, President Jiang Zemin of China, visited Africa in 1996 and recommended key areas that would shape relations between the two partners towards the 21st Century (Michel & Beuret, 2009). These areas included building strong cohesion and cooperation, establishing genuine friendly relations, being co-partners in economic development, and forming strong partnerships towards addressing

developmental challenges on the African continent (Michel & Beuret, 2009). President Jiang Zemin of China was very particular to note that China would not interfere in the domestic issues of Africa unless situations appear to threaten global peace and security (Michel & Beuret, 2009).

Africa's good business climate, natural resources, and readily available labor force; drawing from its high population, make it attractive to China and the international investor community (Hilson & Yakovleva, 2007). As such, China has shown increasing significant interest particularly in natural resource zones in Africa (Hilson & Yakovleva). This interest has been facilitated by the greed and the corruption that is preventing some African leaders from negotiating on behalf of their countries in the interest of their people, hence leading to the exploitation of natural resources in some African states by China. This perception may have shaped or influenced Ghana-Sino relations from the beginning of the Millennium.

Findings from studies by (Hilson and Yakovleva; Michel and Beuret), were of significant relevance to this qualitative exploratory case study because these explained how some Chinese nationals and companies in some African states, are taking advantage of bilateral relations to exploit natural resources in some African states. The focus of studies by (Hilson and Yakovleva, 2007; Michel and Beuret, 2009), was on how Ghana-Sino relations have been influenced from the beginning of the Millennium which is different from the focus of this qualitative exploratory case study which focused on how the bilateral relations between Ghana and China have contributed to illegal mining activities in Ghana with its attendant implications on Ghana's environmental security. This gap is what this qualitative explorative case study has filled by

utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

China's Foreign Direct Investments in Africa

Taylor (2010) explained that though China had tried to maintain a friendly and cordial relation with Africa, that country has always had the ulterior motive since 1960 to gain significant access to the natural resource reserves on the continent. This motive according to (Taylor) has instigated China's increasing injection of Foreign Direct Investments (FDIs) into Africa, as well as providing financial and economic assistance to most African states. The financial assistance and infrastructure developments provided by China to African states have, however, become the bait through which China is increasingly gaining grounds to viable and potential natural mineral zones in Africa (Taylor, 2010).

China usually capitalizes on the greed and corruption of some African leaders and engages in poor or bad practices with specific reference to natural resource extraction from the continent. This has attracted so much criticism from the West, particularly the US calling on China to revise its foreign policy strategies in Africa (Taylor, 2010). Such calls have yielded some little positive results as China in contemporary times appears to be adhering to some international frameworks and conventions for addressing global environmental security threats.

Studies by Taylor, have contributed significantly to the relevance of this qualitative exploratory collective case study. This is because they reveal how China's foreign direct investments in Ghana, have led some Chinese

nationals in some parts of Ghana to take advantage to engage in illegal mining activities in Ghana. The focus of his works was however not on how China's investments in Africa have contributed to illegal mining activities in Ghana with its attendant implications on environmental security. This gap is what this qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled, by utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

China and International Environmental Frameworks

Taylor (2010) explained that the foreign policy direction and strategy of China in Africa forestalls enduring commitments and approaches towards achieving good governance on the continent. This is because most African states just kowtow to the whims and caprices as dictated by China without ensuring or monitoring that any conformity to best practices by China is maintained in their relations. Consequently, China's neglect or non-adherence to best practices, concerning mineral extraction has led to dire environmental security threats in most African states.

Taylor believes that China may have no choice but to abide by best practices in their cooperation, especially with regards to natural resource extraction in Africa. He also suggested the international community should put in measures geared towards ensuring improved labor standards and environmental regulations, especially regarding natural mineral extraction. This will ensure that some natural resources which have been labeled as cursed on the African continent are effectively utilized for the economic

development and well-being of the people on the continent, rather than serving as a source of tensions, conflicts, and wars.

Taylor's study was critical in appreciating the relevance of this qualitative exploratory collective case study. It uncovers the motive behind China's growing interest in Africa's natural resources and energy sectors and also suggests best practices to regulate China and Africa's natural resources relations. The focus of Taylor's study however did not include illegal mining activities by some Chinese and the implications for Africa's environmental security. This gap is what this qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled, by utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

Review of Recently Published Literature on African-Sino Relations

Ceci et al (2014), explain recently published literature in academia as scholarly works which are not more than a decade old (i.e., 10 years). This section of this qualitative exploratory collective case study reviewed recently published works on the nature and scope of African-Sino relations with a particular focus on the involvement of the Chinese in illegal mining and its implications on Ghana's environmental security. The discussions are divided into sub-themes which include: (i) African-Sino relations; (ii) Ghana-Sino relations; (iii) Ghana's environmental and illegal natural resource extraction by some Chinese in Ghana; and (iv) Ghana environmental protection policy.

African-Sino Relations

Chun (2013) noted improvement in diplomatic and economic relations between Africa and China following the end of the Cold War in 1991. The Chinese Government in 2019 assured of the maintenance of friendly relations with Africa towards serving the interest of both Africans and Chinese by adopting new strategic partnerships towards development in Africa (Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs - MOFA, 2019; Gu et al, 2016; Saighi, 2015). This stance by the Chinese Government has engendered improved economic, political, intellectual, social, and cultural cooperation between Africa and China through new treaties and related negotiations (Chinese MOFA, 2019; Jackson, 2018; Khan, 2013).

Chun (2013), further points out the nature and dynamics in the current international development system necessitates that Africa-Sino relations consider new trends towards the strategic development of both partners. Chun established that African states could take advantage of current African-Sino relations to chart new paths towards the development of Africa. He, therefore, recommends that African states should ensure that their relations with China in contemporary times should lead to institutional capacity building with much prominence of fortifying civil society groups and state institutions to regulate and nurture relations between the two partners. Chun also admonished China to foster improved public diplomacy between the two partners to showcase the transfer of shared cultures and values.

The focus of study by (Chun), was on the nature and dynamics of Post-Cold War Africa-Sino relations and how future relations could be improved towards the promotion of development between the two partners which is

different from the focus of this qualitative exploratory collective case study, which focused on how the bilateral relations between Ghana and China have contributed to illegal mining activities in Ghana with its attendant implications on Ghana's environmental security. This gap is what this qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled by utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

Ghana-Sino Relations

China and Ghana have enjoyed a strong bilateral relationship since 1960 which has included significant levels of presidential and diplomatic visits between the two states (Deng, 2011). President Nkrumah visited China during this period which was reciprocated by Premier Zhou Enlai (Deng). In 2002, H.E President John Agyekum Kufuor of Ghana visited China, and this motivated China's President Hu Jintao to reciprocate with a visit to Ghana in 2003.

In 2007, Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao visited Ghana and in September 2010, Ghana's President, H.E. John Evans Atta Mills reciprocated with a visit to China (Carmody, 2017). The Vice-Chairman of the Standing Committee of the National People's Congress of China, Zhou Tienong, paid a visit to Ghana and met with Ghana's then Vice President HE John Dramani Mahama in November 2011(Deng, 2011). These visits were aimed at strengthening bilateral relations between the two states.

In 2018, H.E. President Nana Addo Danquah Akufo-Addo was welcomed as one of Africa's leaders who attended the Beijing Summit on

China Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), (GhanaWeb Online News, 2019). President Akufo-Addo, at the summit, asked his Chinese partner to improve cooperation between the two states, noting that Ghana needs China's assistance to develop (GhanaWeb Online News, 2019). This led to the signing of eight co-operation agreements and memoranda of understanding between Ghana and China, in different sectors of their respective economies.

The agreements included a memorandum on regional aviation co-operation, the one belt, one road memorandum of understanding, co-operation to carry out maternal and child health projects, and agreement for co-operation in the peaceful use of nuclear energy. Other frameworks included co-operation on the expansion of the Cape Coast stadium, co-operation on the supply of police vehicles to the Ghana Police Service, economic co-operation on phase two project of the University of Health and Allied Sciences, Ho, a framework agreement on financing insurance co-operation (\$2 billion Sino-Hydro deal), (GhanaWeb Online News, 2019).

The focus of the studies by (Deng, 2011 and Carmody), was on how Ghana-Sino relations, started in the 1960s and had fostered bilateral relations and economic development in Ghana, which is different from the focus of this qualitative exploratory collective case study which explored how contemporary Ghana-Sino relations have induced illegal mining activities by some Chinese which may have serious environmental security ramifications on Ghana. This gap is what this qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled by utilizing the theory of ecological footprint to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some

Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana.

Ghana's Environmental Security and Illegal Natural Resource Extraction by some Chinese in Ghana

Bansah et al, (2016), established that small-scale mining contributes significantly to the economic development of Ghana. There has been a proliferation of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana which poses dire environmental security threats in most gold resource regions in the country. Bansah et al (2016) noted that illegal gold mining by some Chinese in Ghana has led to the creation of enclaves and deep pits/holes and have consequently resulted in severe injuries to some farmers and death to inhabitants and mostly hunters and farmers in gold resource regions who are oblivious of such enclaves and pits. They also revealed that there have been limited conscious efforts by Chinese illegal miners to protect and safeguard the natural environment as well as ensure the security of citizens in the country. Bansah et al, also established that dust and fumes from illegal mining activities perpetrated by some Chinese in Ghana have serious health implications for inhabitants in areas where such practices are carried out.

Oduro et al., (2015), asserted that the increasing phenomenon of deforestation by some Chinese nationals in Ghana has caused great environmental and economic security dangers to areas, especially where timber, particularly rosewood is exported. The authors argued that deforestation by some Chinese nationals in Ghana has become a topical issue because it has ramifications for biodiversity sustainability, rural livelihood development, and carbon emission. The authors pointed that the lack of

enforcement by the Forestry Commission of Ghana and corruption among local nationals have significantly resulted in the indiscriminate phenomenon of deforestation in Ghana, particularly in northern Ghana with dire environmental security challenges. They, therefore, suggested that to safeguard and protect Ghana's environmental security amidst Chinese growing interest in rosewood, the Government of Ghana should adopt effective measures to minimize the indiscriminate lumbering and deforestation of rosewood particularly, by some Chinese in Ghana to encourage forest reserve conservation and promotion of sustainable forest management.

Rupp (2013) argued that following the discovery of oil in Ghana in 2017, several foreign investors, including China have shown interest in the Jubilee oil field in the Gulf of Guinea. This is because Ghana's oil reserve though not enough is considered to be of very high quality. Despite the oil reserve in Ghana, there is an erratic energy supply in terms of electricity to most parts of the country.

Rupp explained that the interruptions in Ghana's energy supply have led to China showing interest to finance Ghana's oil and energy sectors, thereby, paving way for a new form of bilateral relations between the two states. The proposal by China has not yielded positive feedback due to power-play between the states (Rupp). This is because China seeks to gain significant control and access to Ghana's energy and resource sectors by providing technical and financial support whilst Ghana is adamant to be in control and charge of its oil and energy sectors.

Consequent to the above, (Rupp, 2013), noted that there is much pressure on the Government of Ghana to accept the proposal by China to

finance, design, and build infrastructure to modify and transform Ghana's energy sector. Nevertheless, the Government is also firm to address the challenges of the country's energy sector without relying on foreign partners. The situation has modified Ghana-Sino relations anchored predominantly on the two sensitive sectors of the economy which are energy and oil (Rupp, 2013).

The focus of the studies by (Bansah et al, 2016; Oduro et al.; 2015; and Rupp, 2013), was on how China's key interest in Ghana's gold, timber, energy, and oil sectors and how these have influenced a larger extent bilateral relations between the two states, which is different from the focus of this qualitative exploratory collective case study which explored how contemporary Ghana-Sino relations have induced illegal mining activities by some Chinese which have serious environmental security ramifications on Ghana. This gap is what this qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled, by utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

Ghana's Environmental Protection Policy

An environmental protection policy is a written document geared towards tackling dire ecological risks and threats prevailing in a geographical region (Demortain, 2020). The institution responsible for implementing Ghana's environmental protection policy is the Environmental Protection Agency [EPA], (Tuokuu et al, 2018). The policy is made up of legislation and regulations addressing challenges and threats associated with the environment including waste and sanitation management, pollution, and land degradation

(Tuokuu et al). The Policy includes preventive strategies in addressing Ghana's environmental issues, challenges, and risks.

Ghana's environmental protection policy consists of regulations and legislations geared toward environmental pollution, sanitation, and waste management in the country. The policy adopts the preventive approach, which takes into consideration the socio-economic concerns of Ghanaians to address environmental problems, threats, and issues in the country (EPA, 2019). Towards this end, the EPA liaises with Ghana's lands and minerals commission to ensure that extraction and mining of natural resources do not jeopardize the development and environmental security of the country (EPA). This is because Ghana seeks to implement strategies and approaches for the extraction and utilization of natural resources in ways that do not affect the environmental and human security of Ghanaians.

Ghana's environmental protection policy also ensures that appropriate measures are observed to safeguard the ecosystem from destructive or harmful environmental practices which deteriorate or degrade the quality of the natural environment (EPA). The primary role of Ghana's EPA is to supervise, implement, coordinate, and enforce regulations and legislation essential for protecting and safeguarding the ecosystem in the country (Tuokuu et al, 2018). Also, the EPA is responsible for the dissemination of emerging environmental security in any part of the country and providing coherent frameworks and interventions aimed at addressing them. In other words, the EPA ensures stakeholder consultations and grassroots participation in addressing environmental issues and threats in the country.

Notwithstanding the above-detailed functions and roles supposed to be carried by Ghana's EPA, some businesses, investments, and projects undertaken especially by foreign nationals like the Chinese in the country do not have environmental impact assessment (EIA) certification before the commencement of their operations. This is partly because some of these foreign nationals operate clandestinely under unfair or illegal means without proper supervision or oversight of the EPA. This mostly results in the deterioration and degradation of Ghana's natural environment. Such practices have consequently affected the environmental security of Ghana to a very large extent, with specific reference to illegal mining by some Chinese nationals in the country.

There is however a dearth of scholarly exploration of the challenges faced by Ghana's EPA in addressing the challenges of environmental security, concerning illegal mining operations by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. This qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled this literature gap, by utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

Gaps in the Literature

A significant amount of research has been carried out on illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Africa and the implications for the continent's environmental security. The review of literature, however, showed that little has been explored on how illegal mining activities by some Chinese have impacted Ghana's environmental safety, with specific reference to

contemporary conditions in Ghana-Sino relations. These constitute the major research gaps which this qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled.

This qualitative exploratory collective case study focused on the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals on Ghana's environment. Findings provided insights to fill the literature gap in the reviewed extant literature and thereby contributed new knowledge to the world of academia and beyond. Insights obtained from the experts who were purposively selected provided a greater understanding of the threat of illegal mining by some Chinese in Ghana and measures to curb the phenomenon.

Chapter Summary

Relevant scholarly works were reviewed in chapter two to provide a detailed understanding of environmental security challenges, with regards to China's interest in Africa's natural resources. Most of the existing literature reviewed, made use of a qualitative approach in analyzing challenges of environmental security in Africa and precisely, Ghana with specific reference to illegal natural resource extraction by some Chinese in Ghana. In addition, the concept of environmental security was reviewed using the theory of ecological footprint to ascertain the implications of illegal natural resource extraction (such as illegal gold mining) for Ghana's ecological security.

The literature review concentrated on five main sub-sections including, theoretical framework, literature search, seminal works on China's illegal mineral extraction in Africa, recently published works on African-Sino relations, and gaps in the literature. The major gap identified in the literature

reviewed reflected the limited existence of peer-reviewed literature on the impact of illegal mining activities by some Chinese in Ghana on Ghana's environmental security. This qualitative exploratory collective case study has filled, by utilizing the theory of EF to explore the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODS

Introduction

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory collective case study was to explore the nature and scope of Ghana-Sino relations with a particular focus on the involvement of some Chinese in illegal mining and implications on environmental security in the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana. The purpose of the study was achieved through purposive interviews of 12 participants who have in-depth knowledge on environmental security threats posed by activities of some Chinese nationals involved in illegal mining in Africa, with a special focus on Ghana. Chapter three discusses the research methods used for data collection and analysis to arrive at findings and consists of the research design, study area, population, sampling procedure, data collection instruments, data collection procedures, data processing and analysis, and chapter summary.

Research Design

The research design refers to the practical procedures or steps a researcher follows or adopts in an investigation or exploring a social or scientific problem (Kumar, 2019). This study relied on a qualitative research method and methodology for data collection and analysis. Qualitative research involves the adoption of research methods for the collection and analysis of non-numeric data contrary to what pertains to quantitative research methods. According to (Myers, 2013), qualitative research involves designed sets of techniques to enable researchers to obtain an understanding of the immediate social-cultural surroundings within which people live. The goal of qualitative

research is to attain an insider's view of the group under study. Qualitative research produces general understandings of rich, contextual, and generally unstructured, non-numeric data through conversations with research participants in a natural setting (Rovai et al, 2013).

This qualitative exploratory collective case study employed the interpretivists, exploratory and descriptive qualitative research designs. Ponelis (2015) pointed out that the qualitative approach gives valued results required for interpretivists to fully comprehend contexts. Thus, qualitative methods are reinforced by interpretivists, because the paradigm portrays a world in which reality is socially constructed (Ponelis). The interpretivists approach was used to explain the influence of illegal mining by some Chinese nationals on environmental security as this relates to Ghana.

Exploratory design most often relies on secondary research such as reviewing available literature or data and also conducting in-depth interviews, case studies, and pilot studies (Dellinger & Leech, 2007). This study employed the exploratory qualitative research design to clarify ambiguous factors (i.e. environmental security and illegal mining) of the objectives of the study. The exploratory and descriptive designs helped in providing extra information where limited information existed and also helped to show gaps in the existing literature.

The exploratory design was employed due to the flexibility or non-rigid nature of the qualitative research method. The method involves exploring other avenues of obtaining data without strict restrictions and applications as in the case of the quantitative research method. The qualitative design helped in the formulation of the problem statement (Shields & Rangarjan, 2013). The

design also helped in exploring the phenomenon of illegal mining without explicit expectations (Shields & Rangarjan). This is because the design helped in making holistic investigation and analysis about data obtained from sources indicated earlier without any prejudices or personal sentimentality. The descriptive design was used to establish facts and relationships; by describing in detail the status quo of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana and the implications of such activities for Ghana's environmental security. This study described the key approaches and strategies adopted by the Chinese in their illegal mining activities and the ramifications they have for environmental security in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, of the Western region of Ghana.

Study Area

Awodua is a district in the Western region of Ghana. It is located between latitude 400'N and 500 40'N and longitudes 10 45' W and 20 10'W (Mantey et al, 2017). It is bounded to the north by the Wassa Amenfi East District, to the south by the Ahanta West District, to the West by the Nzema East Municipal, and to the East by Mpohor Wassa East district. The municipality has a total land area of 2354 km² (Mantey et al). There are several gold mines situated in the region and the district also has the region's only public university; the University of Mines and Technology (Mantey et al).

The Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district is one of the richest in Ghana in terms of natural resources with a preponderance of gold resources. Similar to Obuasi in the Ashanti region, gold is the major natural resource deposit in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, and

thus, has led to the proliferation of illegal mining activities including those perpetrated by some Chinese nationals in the area. This made the selection of the study area justifiable for exploration of the influence of illegal mining on environmental security.

Population

Bhattacharjee (2012) defines the target population as the whole set of elements that are selected by the researcher for investigation. A target population is the set of elements selected by a researcher for investigation (Draugalis & Plaza, 2009). The target population had the specific and key characteristics that were required for the study. Since the study focused only on an exploration of the influence of illegal mining on environmental security; the population included six inhabitants of the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana, officials of Minerals Commission and Lands Commission in Ghana, officials of the EPA, research fellow at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, officials at the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation in Ghana, and officials of the Ghana Armed Forces (involved in Operation Vanguard to check illegal mining activities across the country).

Sampling Procedure

Sampling is a process used in statistical analysis in which a predetermined number of observations are taken from a larger population (Etikan et al., 2016). The methodology used to sample from a larger population depends on the type of analysis being performed, but it may include simple random sampling or systematic sampling (Etikan et al.). There are two main types of sampling techniques for determining the sample size for

carrying out research work (Noor, 2008). These are probability and non-probability sampling techniques.

Probability sampling is where elements of the population are known, which means that the researchers have the list of the population and all sampling elements have a chance to be selected (Noor). With non-probability sampling, the elements in a population are unknown (Noor). Thus, the probability of selection for each element is unknown. This qualitative explorative collective case study made use of non-probability procedures since the researcher cannot collect the full list of the target population elements in the study area and various state institutions responsible for safeguarding Ghana's environmental security.

Sampling Technique

This qualitative exploratory collective case study utilized the convenience and purposive non-probability sampling procedures for data collection and analysis. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling procedure where participants or subjects included in a particular study are selected due to their convenience or proximity to the researcher (Cohen & Arieli, 2011). This method was chosen for the study because subjects/respondents to be interviewed were purposively selected whilst on duty at work or based on their availability in the study area. This is due to the busy schedule of some of the respondents, as well as the difficulty to get them to provide responses that were relevant for data analysis. A purposive sampling technique according to (Cohen and Arieli, 2011) involves intentionally selecting units of the sample population for particular research based on the purpose of the research study.

Sampling Size

The sample size for a research project is important because it could affect the result of a study (Mason, 2010). A proper sampling design should follow an effective sample size to get an accurate result from the research project (Ross, 2005). This qualitative exploratory research design included views of twelve purposively selected experts including, one official from the Minerals Commission, one official of the Lands Commission in Ghana, one lecturer at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, one official from the Environment Protection Agency (EPA), one official at the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation in Ghana, one official from the Ghana Armed Forces, and six inhabitants in the Awodua community. The experts were purposively selected based on having adequate and in-depth knowledge on illegal mining activities being perpetrated by some Chinese within the Wassa-Amenfi District of the Western region of Ghana.

Data Collection Instruments

Secondary data was collected from journal articles, books, news reports, newspaper articles, video documentaries, and commentaries on the subject matter of environmental security in Africa and Ghana in particular. Primary data was collected through an interview guide, containing eight questions to collect data from experts through an audio recorder or handwriting and at the convenience of the designated experts.

Data Collection Procedures

Data are information gathered and collected based on the research purpose (Pienta et al., 2010). Data collection is one of the most important

aspects of any research study. Ritchie et al (2013) explain that research can be conducted with different methods, but every research is based on the data which is analyzed and further clarified to get information. There are two main methods of data collection. These are primary data and secondary data.

Primary Data Collection Procedures

Primary data is collected from first-hand sources which have not been published yet and the data is more reliable, accurate and objective (Pienta et al., 2010). In this qualitative exploratory collective case study, primary data was obtained through unstructured expert interviews from six inhabitants in the Awodua community, an official at the Lands Commission, an official at the Minerals and Lands Commissions, an official at Ghana's Environmental Protection Agency, a Research Fellow at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, an official at the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation in Ghana and an official of the Ghana Armed).

Secondary Data Collection Procedures

Secondary data refers to existing data that has been obtained by other researchers and has been published previously (Silverman, 2016). This qualitative exploratory collective case study utilized secondary sources including Ghana EPA, Lands, and Mineral Commissions official documents. Journal articles, books, news reports, newspaper articles, theses, video documentaries, and commentaries were also considered. All these data sources were reviewed in addition to the general literature on environmental security due to illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Africa, to identify gaps for this qualitative exploratory collective case study, with a specific focus

on the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana. Internet websites where relevant data pertinent to the topic could be obtained were also sought.

Online copies of relevant books and articles were downloaded whilst hard copy materials were obtained through libraries of various educational institutions such as the University of Ghana (UG), Ghana Armed Forces Command and Staff College (GAFSCS), Legon Center for International Affairs and Diplomacy (LECIAD), KAIPTC – Kofi Annan International Peacekeeping Training Centre and Nyansapo College, whilst others were purchased.

Data Processing and Analysis

Data Processing

The document content analysis approach was the basis for processing and concluding secondary data in this qualitative exploratory collective case study. This involved making inferences from secondary data concerning primary data gathered from interviews to draw a logical conclusion for the study. Content analysis is a research technique used to make replicable and valid inferences by interpreting and coding textual material (Merriam, 2009). This allowed for reviewing several existing literature on the topic which aided in making objective holistic analysis of the topic rather than relying on personal judgments. Audio recordings and field notes collected from interviews were transcribed and translated word-for-word into meaningful data. The transcribed data was imported to NVivo12® software and examined for common themes which were obtained through analysis and coding.

Data Analysis

Data collected from interviews were analyzed thematically. This was done in alignment with the research objectives. Unlike quantitative data such as questionnaires and surveys in which codes are usually numbers, the data for this qualitative exploratory case study used labels to assign codes to data that was remembered easily before grouping them into the various thematic areas. The data analysis was aided by the utilization of the theory of ecological footprint to enhance the analysis of the environmental security implications of illegal mining by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, of the Western region of Ghana. The second phase of data analysis involved transcribing, coding, and generating themes from the interview data of 12 participants with the help of NVivo12® software.

Chapter Summary

Chapter three specifies the research methodology which was used to collect relevant data for analysis. Data collection was done in two-fold involving (i) content analysis of data on the environmental security in Africa and Ghana to be specific and (ii) application of qualitative exploratory collective case study approach in the collection of primary data from the twelve experts on the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the country, with focus on Awodua district in the Western region of Ghana as a research site. Secondary data were used to triangulate primary data from the experts.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory collective case study was to explore the nature and scope of Ghana-Sino relations with a particular focus on the involvement of some Chinese in illegal mining and implications on environmental security in the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana. The purpose of the study was achieved through purposive interviews of 12 participants who have in-depth knowledge on environmental security threats posed by activities of some Chinese nationals involved in illegal mining in Africa, with a special focus on Ghana. Findings from the study established the negative effect of illegal mining by some Chinese in the Awodua district in the Western region of Ghana.

Chapter four presents an analysis of findings from interview data on illegal mining and Ghana's environmental security. The chapter focuses on the application of findings from the study to address the research questions. Data collected through the use of interview questions were edited and coded before being analyzed. Towards this end, the data analysis was based on the research questions and objectives of this study. The chapter presents an analysis and discussion of the data that was collected from the 12 experts. It is organized into the following sections: data collection, participant demographics, findings from research interviews, and chapter summary. The findings from interview data are organized into six themes and presented in Table 3.

Data Collection

This qualitative exploratory case study involved two phases of data collection; from relevant information from the journal articles, books, news reports, newspaper articles and interview data from 12 participants via face-to-face digitally recorded interviews that used eight unstructured questions. The purpose of the interview was to understand the environmental security threats posed by activities of some Chinese nationals involved in illegal mining in Ghana, with a special focus on Awodua. The use of interviews and document analysis as data collection instruments was to develop a comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under study to ensure triangulation (Salkind, 2010).

First phase of Data Collection

Secondary data and information were perused from some scholarly materials to supplement, buttress and lend credence to the assertions, views, and dispositions of the research participants engaged in this study. Such scholarly works include the works of (Ayee, 2012; Bansah et al, 2016; Crawford et al., 2015; Crawford & Botchwey, 2017; Horner, 2020; Hilson et al, 2014; Rupp, 2013). Some news portals were also perused to confirm the evidence provided by the research participants. Such news portals include GhanaWeb News and the South China Morning Post. Relevant data from social media handles of the Ghana Armed forces revealed increased security efforts by the Army to curb the menace of illegal mining in the Western region. Illegal mining has always been a challenge. Data from the Minerals Commission revealed an influx of the menace by foreigners specifically the Chinese from the year 2012. Identified relevant information served as input for

data analysis that applied document analysis methodology as elaborated in Chapter 3

Second Phase of Data Collection

Data collection for this study involved the search for relevant information from 12 research participants via face-to-face digitally recorded interviews that used eight semi-structured questions. Interview participants for this study were categorized into two groups: six government officials (made up of one official from each of the following; Ghana Armed Forces, Minerals Commission, Lands Commission, Environmental Protection Agency, Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation, and Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana), and six inhabitants of Awodua (made up of; traditional leader, assemblyman, medical doctor, registered small scale miner, teacher, and farmer). Each of these 12 participants was purposefully selected and their consent was individually sought. The purpose of the interview was to explore the nature and scope of Ghana-Sino relations with a particular focus on the involvement of some Chinese in illegal mining and implications on environmental security in the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana.

These participants were contacted via phone and emails to sign the informed consent forms which were sent to them before the interview was consequently scheduled. The interviews with officials from the GAF, Minerals Commission, Lands Commission, EPA, Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation, and Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana were conducted via phone from 2nd-7th November 2020. The interviews with the six indigenes of Awodua (made up

of; traditional leader, assemblyman, medical doctor, registered small scale miner, teacher, and farmer) were conducted from 12th- 21st November 2020. The interviews lasted between 20 to 25 minutes. The difference in actual time spent per participant compared with the projection made during the preparation of the interview protocol was as a result of over projection of time for the study. The length of the interview duration, however, did not affect the credibility and quality of the responses from participants.

Primary data collected was transcribed for each of the respondents that were interviewed. The responses to the questions were then coded using NVivo12®. The outcome of this study and commonly occurring themes for each question were grouped under defined nodes. The results of this study were achieved through the analysis of emergent themes.

Demographics of Participants

Twelve respondents were interviewed via digitally recorded interviews. Participants' consent was individually obtained. Research participants were categorized into two groups: six government officials (made up of one official from each of the following; Ghana Armed Forces, Minerals Commission, Lands Commission, Environmental Protection Agency, Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation, and Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana) and: six inhabitants of Awodua (made up of; traditional leader, assemblyman, medical doctor, registered small scale miner, teacher, and farmer). Table 1 illustrates the demographic data of participants which includes participants' gender and level of education.

Table 1: Demographic Data of Participants by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
	N=12	
Male	9	75
Female	3	25

Source: Fieldwork (2021)

Table 1 shows the gender distribution of participants and revealed more males: 9 (75%) than females: 3 (25%) participated in this study.

Table 2: Demographic Data of Participants by level of education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
	N=12	
Basic school certificate	1	8.3
Secondary school certificate	2	16.7
Tertiary school certificate	9	75

Source: Fieldwork (2021)

Table 2 shows that a majority of the participants had relatively higher level of education with an aggregate of 9 participants (75%) having attained tertiary education certificate.

Findings from Document Analysis

China's interest to gain access to global natural resources is not a recent phenomenon. However, this interest by China has gained increasing momentum in Africa at the beginning of the Millennium particularly East Africa, due to the abundance of natural resources in that region (Hilson et al, 2014). Even though China's bilateral relation with Ghana is traced back to the

1960s, China's increasing interest in Ghana's gold resources became much pronounced from 2008, when the increase in gold prices on the international market led to the significant interest for global gold resources which saw the significant inflow of Chinese miners into Ghana (Crawford et al., 2015).

Subsequently, especially after 2010, the Chinese have also shown interest in the mining industry in Ghana. As a result, The South China Morning Post, which is a Chinese newspaper, reported in 2013, that an estimated 50,000 miners had left China for Ghana (South China Morning Post, August 23, 2013). This shows that there has been a significant increase in the influx of Chinese nationals to Ghana to gain access to the gold resources in the country. By the end of 2013, it was reported that a significant number of Chinese nationals who were resident in Ghana were engaged in casual and illegal gold mining with the use of Chinese excavators, which pose dire environmental security threats and therefore necessitated the Ghanaian Government to take urgent steps towards addressing the menace (Crawford & Botchwey, 2017).

On the canker of corruption (Ayee et al, 2011), posited that the canker of corruption has become more pronounced in Ghana's mining sector as some Chinese nationals who are resident in the country try to subvert government and security personnel and institutions and make most of them become corrupt to be able to engage in illicit mining activities. This is generating a culture of corruption as a way of life for survival in contemporary Ghanaian society.

(Rupp, 2013), contends that there is much pressure on the Government of Ghana to accept the proposal by China to finance, design, and build infrastructure to modify and transform Ghana's energy sector. Consequently,

some Chinese nationals illegally enter Ghana which has rich gold resource deposits, to engage in illegal mining activities to feed growing demands back home in China. This has led to the illegal mining and exploitation of gold resources by some Chinese in Ghana to feed local Chinese industries back home, thereby contributing to the environmental security threats experienced in most parts of the country.

On the implications of illegal mining (galamsey) on the environment (Bansah et al, 2016) explained that illegal small-scale mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana pose dire environmental security threats to Ghanaians since such activities result in the creation of deep pits, holes, and enclaves which have led to untimely deaths and severe injuries to some farmers, hunters, and inhabitants who are unaware of such pits. For example, in July 2019, seven people were reported trapped and died in a Galamsey pit in Obuasi (GhanaWeb News, July 8, 2019, pp 5). Sometimes, when it rains, water may also likewise collect in pits and openings, making them potential breeding zones for mosquitoes. More often than not, mosquitoes and other wild animals, find these openings or shafts habitable to breed which also pose further security threats to neighboring communities through the spread of Malaria.

Activities of illegal mining result in the pollution of water bodies in Ghana. In this vein, (Bansah et al, 2016), asserts that Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities, which mostly involve the use of chemicals and explosives, is a major cause of river water contamination in Ghana. This is because it also often leads to the death of fishes which stink and further pollute major water bodies. Bansah et al. have established that illegal small-scale

mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana poses dire health security threats to Ghanaians. This is because such illegal mining activities result in the creation of dust and fumes which pose breathing challenges to inhabitants in areas where such activities take place as witnessed in the Awodua community.

Findings from Interview Data

This section presents the summary of themes that emerged from interview data which are presented based on the objectives of this study. Six themes were generated from the eight interview questions. Responses to the research questions were then coded using the nodes created for each theme.

Summary of themes

A qualitative data analysis computer software referred to as NVivo12® was employed to analyze the interview data gathered from the 12 research participants. Coding data collected from research participants have been defined under themes. Sources represent participants who responded to the research interviews and the number of coding references refers to the number of times a source referenced the theme. This study was guided by four research questions:

1. How have contemporary Ghana-Sino relations facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources?
2. How have illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals influenced Ghana's environmental security?
3. Which challenges have confronted the fight against illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?
4. How can environmental security be improved with specific reference to illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?

The results of the study are presented under six themes that emerged from the analysis of the interview as detailed in Table 3. The themes were generated from the objectives of the study. Themes 1 and 2 addressed research questions 1, regarding how contemporary Ghana-Sino relations have facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources. Theme 1 indicated that there has been an increase in the number of Chinese mining illegally in Ghana. Theme 2 revealed the legal frameworks put in place to permit mining in Ghana.

Themes 3 and 4 addressed research question 2 regarding how illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals have influenced Ghana's environmental security. Theme 5 addressed research question 4 regarding how environmental security can be improved with specific reference to illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. Theme 6 throws more light on research question 4 by looking at the challenges confronting Ghana in addressing environmental security threats due to Chinese illegal mining activities in the country.

Table 3: Summary of Themes from Interview Data

Theme number	Description of themes.
Theme 1	There has been an acceleration of Chinese interest in Ghana's gold resources.
Theme 2	Ghana has an array of Legal frameworks for mining in the country.
Theme 3	There is a surge in Ghana-Sino relations that facilitates the exploitation of Ghana's gold resources.

Theme 4	There are negative environmental security implications of Chinese illegal mining activities in the Awodua community.
Theme 5	Government of Ghana has made significant efforts to curb the prevalence of illegal Chinese mining in Ghana.
Theme 6	Several challenges confront Ghana in addressing environmental security threats due to Chinese illegal mining activities in the country.

Source: Fieldwork (2021)

Lists of key words developed from participants' responses to interview questions are presented in Tables 4. The most frequently used word was *galamsey* (native word for illegal mining (f=624), followed by *Chinese* (f=475) and *poverty* (f=419).

Table 4: Word Frequency: Words over 200 uses

Word	Count	Weighted (%)	Percentage
Galamsey	624	1.33	
Chinese	475	1.19	
Poverty	419	1.25	
Unemployment	385	1.31	
Corruption	366	1.05	
Destroys	336	1.34	
Water Pollution	332	0.96	
Youth	326	0.85	
Land Pollution	314	0.67	
Deforestation	308	0.69	
Excavators	292	1.64	
Media	288	1.23	

Gold	282	0.62
Sound Pollution	274	0.50
Mineral resources	258	4.53
Laws	249	0.49
Operation Vanguard	235	0.92
GAF	217	1.03
Reclamation	208	1.65

Source: Fieldwork (2020)

An example of the use of the words *galamsey* and Chinese are: “The *galamsey* by the Chinese is one of the major security threats to the community of Awodua”. “In my opinion, one of the major challenges to the fight against Chinese *galamsey* is corruption”-Participant RS07. “The *galamsey* activities of the Chinese can be brought to an abrupt end when the government intervenes by sending the soldiers into Awodua. In Ghana, more people fear the soldiers than the police. So it is only when the soldiers are involved in the fight against the Chinese *galamsey* that this security threat can be solved. The government needs to do it as soon as possible if it wants the *galamsey* to end in Awodua.”-Participant RS10.

Other words used more than 300 times included corruption (f=366), destroys (f=336), and water pollution (f=332) – Table 14. Participant RS11 “These illegal miners don’t care about our water bodies. Awodua has just one water body and it has been polluted as a result of the activities of these miners”, Participant RS12 emphasized, “Sometimes the task force of Police and Soldiers do come here but because of corruption, you see the illegal mining still ongoing by these small-eyed white men”. RS01 noted, “The mining does not only destroy our water bodies but it also degrades the land and afterward cannot be used for farming again”.

Table 5, presents relevant words used between 100 and 199 times by participants. They included; proliferation (f=193), challenges (f=190) and environmental security (f=189). For example, Participant RS09 commented, “The proliferation of illegal mining by the foreigners is what has led to the impunity that we witnessing now.” Participant RS02 remarked that “The challenges in the country that facilitate the illegal mining includes corruption, joblessness, economic hardships and a lack of political commitment on the part of the government”.

Table 5: Words used between 100 and 199 times

Word	Count	Weighted Percentage (%)
Proliferation	193	0.40
Challenges	190	0.33
Environmental security	189	0.88
Government	172	0.64
Implications	167	0.59
Support	160	0.52
Regulatory	157	0.72
Protecting	157	0.39
Frameworks	157	0.38
Created	149	0.27
Promoting	145	0.23
Recommendations	142	0.51
Institutions	140	2.61
Operations	134	0.35
Develop	132	0.36
History	129	0.38
Policy	127	0.32
Leadership	125	0.80
Performance	125	0.32
Work Force	118	0.27
Development	115	0.30
Hardship	115	0.26
Sanitation	114	0.23

Security	112	0.29
Collaboration	109	0.27
Finances	109	0.16
Implement	105	0.28
Government	104	0.44
Consultation	103	0.19
Stakeholder	101	0.12
Bilateral Relations	100	0.17

Source: (Fieldwork (2020))

Table 6, reveals relevant words used between 70 and 99 times, including *funding* (f=95), *inter-agency* (f=94) and *objectives* (f=93). For instance, Participant RS01 commented “I suggest that the government and Ministry of Interior and Defense should provide funding for operation Vanguard and Halt in order to sustain it for a longer period of time instead of the adhoc 6 months duration. He again remarked that there is the need for inter-agency collaboration between the security forces, the EPA, the Minerals Commission and the Lands Commission in order to find a lasting solution to illegal mining”. Participant RS08 noted “the objectives of operation Vanguard and Halt come to nothing if it is only for a short period of time”.

Table 6: Words used between 70 and 99 times

Word	Count	Weighted (%)	Percentage
Funding	95	0.36	
Inter-agency	94	0.17	
Objectives	93	0.23	
Program	92	0.39	
Personnel	92	0.32	
Illicit	92	0.19	
Fight	92	0.12	
Chiefs	90	0.47	
Trained	86	0.18	
Foreigners	85	0.38	
Diplomacy	83	0.30	
Welfare	83	0.12	

Mandate	81	0.26
Health	79	0.29
Safeguarding	79	0.18
Practical	78	0.19
Official	76	0.16
Threat	70	0.21

Source: (Fieldwork, 2020)

Theme 1: There has been an acceleration of Chinese interest in Ghana’s gold resources

The first theme generated from the interview data revealed that there has been an increase in Chinese illegal miners in Ghana. The 12 research participants through 46 coded references, 3336 words expressed in 44 paragraphs affirmed that there has been an increased interest in Ghana’s gold resources by Chinese miners (RS01, RS02, RS03, RS04, RS05, RS06, RS07, RS08, RS09, RS10, and RS12). Giving a detailed description of the increased presence of Chinese in Ghana, the respondent from the Minerals Commission indicated that Ghana has had foreign relations with China since the 1960s. However, China’s interest in gold was rekindled in the year 2008 when the increase in the prices of Gold in the international community brought into the country significant foreign exchange. He added that the People’s Republic of China has had a significant interest in the natural resources of the globe since time immemorial. He noted however that at the turn of the Millennium, there was a surge of Chinese’s interest in natural resources from Africa, especially in East Africa due to the abundance of natural resources in the region. The 2008 increase in the prices of gold globally is one of the main factors that motivated the influx of Chinese miners into Ghana (RS 02, 2020).

Subsequently, especially after 2010, the Chinese have also shown interest in the mining industry in Ghana. He added that intelligence reaching

the GAF revealed that an estimated 50,000 miners had left China for Ghana since 2013. The Respondent from the Mineral Commission also added his voice on the significant increase in the influx of Chinese nationals to Ghana to gain access to the gold resources in the country. He noted that by the end of 2013, there was a significant number of Chinese nationals who were resident in Ghana and who were engaged in casual and illegal gold mining with the use of Chinese excavators, which pose dire environmental security threats and therefore necessitated the government of Ghana to take urgent steps towards addressing the menace (RS 02, 2020).

The respondent from the GAF indicated that the increased number of Chinese in illegal mining of gold forced the then President, HE Mr. John Dramani Mahama, on 5th May 2013, to establish the State Inter-Ministerial Task Force to address the challenges of small-scale illegal mining activities, particularly carried out by Chinese nationals in Ghana (RS 01, 2020). In the opinion of the official from the Mineral Commission, this explains why illegal mining activities by some Chinese in Ghana became a topical national issue for Ghana's environmental security. This mounted pressure on the Government to take urgent and drastic measures towards addressing illegal mining by some Chinese, despite the friendly bilateral relations which had existed between China and Ghana since the 1960s (RS 02, 2020).

Theme 2: Ghana has an array of Legal frameworks for mining in the country.

The second theme generated from the interview data revealed that there are legal frameworks regarding the conditions of mining in Ghana. This was shown through 46 coded references from 2155 expressed words in 39

paragraphs. Six respondents (RS01, RS02, RS03, RS04, RS05, RS06,) affirmed that the country has laws on mining in the country. Responding to the legal frameworks on mining in Ghana, the respondent from the Minerals Commission indicated that per the Laws of Ghana, all-natural resources including gold mineral resources are the property of the state, which are under the custody of the President. He cited Article 257(6) of the 1992 Constitution of the Republic of Ghana “Every mineral in its natural state ... is the property of the Republic and is vested in the President in trust for the people of Ghana,” He added that Small scale mining in Ghana was illegal to citizens until 1989 when the Mining Law 1989 (PNDCL 218) regularized and sanctioned the licensing system to make it lawful for Ghanaian citizens to legally partake in such activities. He continued that the situation has been further reinforced by the Minerals and Mining Act 2006(Act 703) which makes it possible for miners to register and acquire a maximum of 25 acres for mining activities sanctioned by the Minerals Commission (RS 02, 2020).

In throwing more light on the legal framework the respondent from the Minerals Commission revealed that despite the above conditions for legally engaging in mining activities in the country, it is estimated that less than 30 percent of miners currently engaged in small scale mining in Ghana are registered with the Mineral Commission, whilst the majority of small-scale miners including foreigners such as the Chinese, do so illegally or unlawfully in the country (RS 02, 2020).

The respondent from the Lands Commission recalled that most illegal small-scale miners are unable and unwilling to register with the Mineral Commission because they claim the system is costly, time-consuming, and

bureaucratic. He also reiterated that the laws of Ghana under no circumstance permit foreigners to engage in small-scale mining activities in the country. Therefore, all foreigners, particularly the Chinese who are engaged in small-scale mining activities in Ghana do so unlawfully or illegally. This is because they do so as illegal employment of foreign nationals, contrary to the Immigration Act, 2000 (Act 573) (RS 03, 2020).

Theme 3: There is a surge in Ghana-Sino relations that facilitates the exploitation of Ghana's gold resources

The third theme generated from interview data revealed contemporary conditions in Ghana-Sino Relations that have facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources. This was shown through 46 coded references from 2555 expressed words in 38 paragraphs. There are several conditions present in Ghana that have facilitated the continuous exploitation of Ghana's gold resources by some Chinese nationals, which have dire implications on Ghana's environmental security. However, this section analyses some of the major contemporary conditions as identified from field data, which include among others, corruption, economic hardship and poverty, institutional inefficiencies and deficiencies, the nature of Ghana's domestic politics, and Ghana's quest for accelerated economic growth amidst bilateral economic relations with China.

Corruption

On conditions that have enhanced the menace; a medical doctor who is an inhabitant of Awodua revealed that some Chinese nationals in Ghana who are involved in illegal mining activities have accomplices and agents among a wide spectrum of top state officials, including government officials, police,

diplomats, politicians, military personnel, traditional authorities, customs Officers, immigration officers, airport Security officials, opinion leaders, ordinary Ghanaian citizens, among others. Most of these top state officials either receive bribes or are given bribes to help promote and facilitate the illegal mining activities of some Chinese nationals in Ghana (RS 09, 2020).

To buttress this point the official, from the Minerals Commission of Ghana, asserted through the interview that, “the canker of corruption is gradually eroding the very moral fiber of the Ghanaian society especially, among government institutions, top state officials, and the general populace, (RS 02, 2020). He added that this is generating a culture of corruption as a way of life for survival in contemporary Ghanaian society. This is because some government institutions and personnel, as well as ordinary Ghana citizens, allowed themselves to be lured by the dictates and monetary packages from Chinese nationals due to harsh economic conditions of the country to bend the law in their favor.

An official from the Minerals Commission of Ghana pointed out that “under the Minerals and Mining Law 2006 (Acts 703), no foreign national in Ghana can engage in small scale mining in the country,” (RP 01, 2020). Nevertheless, some Ghanaian nationals who have been licensed to do so illegally sub-contract or liaise with some Chinese mining companies or nationals to engage in illegal mining activities to exploit Ghana’s gold resources and subsequently degrade the natural environment. Consequently, the prevalence of environmental security threats in the Fourth Republic of Ghana due to the illegal mining activities by some Chinese is due to the pervasive culture of corruption in the country.

Economic hardships and poverty

The respondent from the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, commenting on the economy, indicated that closely related to the canker of corruption is economic hardship and poverty as the major causes of the prevalence of security threats including environmental threats in Ghana, especially due to illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the country. According to him, about 48% of the youth in Ghana are unemployed. Some of these youths, including tertiary graduates who cannot cope with their unemployment situation, have resorted to all sorts of unlawful ways to survive including being employed by some Chinese nationals to engage in illegal mining activities. Consequently, these illegal mining activities have posed dire environmental security threats in areas where such practices occur (RS 06, 2020).

The official from the Ghana Armed Forces who has been involved in both Operation Vanguard formed in 2017 and Operation Halt established in 2020 to stop ‘galamsey’ or illegal mining in Ghana), revealed in an interview that:

Most often, the youths who work with Chinese nationals engaged in illegal mining who are arrested by the task force are people from poor backgrounds who are desperate to do anything possible, including engaging in unlawful ways such as illegal mining as a means of coping with harsh economic conditions they experience (RS 01, 2020)

On this same topic, the traditional leader and the assemblyman shared the same opinion indicating that the current economic hardship and poverty levels in most parts of Ghana, coupled with mass unemployment among

youths (especially graduates), have forced some government officials, chiefs, politicians, community opinion leaders and youths (who usually act as vigilante groups) in entering and promoting illegal business transactions and negotiations with some Chinese in Ghana, as a lucrative avenue or livelihood strategy to make ends meet. These transactions sometimes include illegal mining activities, which consequently have dire environmental security ramifications on the country. This situation has contributed significantly to the increasing phenomenon of environmental security threats posed by Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities in Ghana (RS 07, RS 08, 2020).

Institutional inefficiencies and deficiencies

The respondent from the Lands Commission on the topic of institutional capacity revealed that institutional inefficiencies and deficiencies in some state security apparatuses and government institutions have contributed significantly to the increasing exploitation of Ghana's gold resources by some Chinese companies and nationals in Ghana, which have also led to drastic environmental security threats. He noted that there are key state institutions in Ghana engendered and mandated for safeguarding and preserving the country's environmental security, especially with regards to natural resource extraction such as gold mining in Ghana. He revealed that:

“The Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources has the overall responsibility for the mining industry. It is responsible for granting mining and exploration licenses and ensures that all individuals and organizations who engage in mining and exploration activities without a license are prosecuted by law since they will be doing so illegally.”

However, there are challenges for the Ministry in identifying some

Chinese engaged in illegal mining activities in Ghana, to be sanctioned (RS 03, 2020).

Also, the official from the Environment Protection Agency (EPA) revealed through an interview that:

The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) ensures that the activities of Public and Private Companies or operators do not harm the environment and water bodies to pose health threats to surrounding inhabitants. Notwithstanding the role of EPA to help protect and preserve Ghana's natural environment, some Chinese nationals in Ghana continue to pose dire environmental consequences in areas such as the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana through activities of illegal mining (RS 04, 2020).

In addition, the official from the Minerals Commission revealed in an interview that:

The Minerals Commission is responsible for legislation that affects mining and mining explorations in Ghana. Therefore, the Commission ensures that mining and exploration policies safeguard the health needs of the people, and are carried out in an environmentally friendly manner and also done in a way that will increase the revenue base of the government for development. Towards this end, it recommends to the government to help curb the incidence of illegal mining since it is environmentally unfriendly, poses health threats to surrounding inhabitants, and also deprives the government of substantial revenue for development. Notwithstanding this function by the Commission, there are some foreigners, particularly some Chinese who are still

engaged in illegal mining in areas such as the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana which pose great environmental security risks in such areas (RS 02, 2020)

The official from the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology, and Innovation in Ghana in an interview revealed that:

The Ministry of Environment, Science, and Technology (MEST) also ensures that the mining activities done anywhere in Ghana are consistent with the country's environmental policies and objectives. Notwithstanding the functions of the above institutions, illegal mining activities by some Chinese in areas such as the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana is still rife (RS 05, 2020)

Furthermore, the official from the Ghana Armed Forces (involved in Operations Vanguard and Halt to check illegal mining activities across the country) revealed in an interview that:

Where there are inefficiencies and deficiencies in state's institutions to maintain law and order, it is more likely for some section of the population as well as foreign nationals to take the law into their hands and misbehave, knowing very well that the systems are not functioning properly to identify them, let alone prosecute them for their illegal activities such as the prevalence of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana (RS 01, 2020).

The revelations from the research participants lend credence to the assertion that where state institutions fail to perform their functions effectively to provide adequate security for all individuals in the country, this creates an avenue for foreigners to pursue illegality with impunity as observed in illegal

mineral extraction by some Chinese in Ghana. The courts do not have strong punitive sanctions for citizens involved in the menace of galamsey. In a similar vein, the judicial system and the courts are incapacitated to sanction foreign nationals such as the Chinese who engage in illegal activities including illegal extraction of Ghana's natural resources. This gives impetus for such foreigners to continue in their illegal activities which have negative consequences on the environment.

The nature of Ghana's domestic politics

The nature of politicking as witnessed in Ghana has led to the monetization of politics and indiscipline. In an interview with the lecturer at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, he points out that:

The nature of domestic politics in Ghana which is perpetuated along ethnic and religious lines has led to discrimination and some injustices which have given much impunity to some sections of the population to disregard the Rule of Law and perpetuate criminal activities with such great impunity. These include local citizens receiving bribes from some Chinese expatriates and facilitating their engagement in illegal mining activities in the country. In other instances, most politicians in Ghana usually pursue political agenda to promulgate and safeguard the interests of foreign nationals including the Chinese to be able to receive funding during electioneering periods. As such some Ghanaian politicians usually employ all means possible including the use of force, violence, and aggression to sometimes intimidate or oppress other citizens who do not align to their bidding of foreign nationals

who promote their interests. Some Chinese in Ghana have taken advantage of the current socio-political environment to liaise with some politicians, security personnel, and government officials to propagate their clandestine operations such as illegal mining activities which usually have dire ramifications on Ghana's environmental security including the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana (RS 06, 2020)

Ghana's quest for accelerated economic growth amidst bilateral economic relations with China

In an interview with the lecturer at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, he revealed that:

The current international development system which is characterized by globalization has made it imperative for states to depend on each other for the realization of their political-economic goals. This has further facilitated the movement of people from geographical region to another or one country to another, just as some Chinese nationals travel to Ghana. However, Ghana's quest for economic development has made her open her doors for foreign investors including Chinese investors. Ghana is a cash-trap to receive economic assistance from China, which China is ever ready to provide to accelerate economic development in Ghana without meddling in the internal affairs of Ghana. Some Chinese nationals and companies have taken advantage of the situation to penetrate the core natural resource and energy sectors of Ghana (RS 06, 2020).

Theme 4: There are negative environmental security implications of Chinese illegal mining activities in the Awodua community.

This section analyzes some dire environmental security threats which bedevil the Awodua Community of the Wassa-Amenfi District, in the Western region of Ghana due to Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities in the region. This was shown through 46 coded references from 2115 expressed words in 35 paragraphs. Six respondents (RS07, RS08, RS09, RS10, RS11, and RS12) corroborated evidence of environmental security implications in the Awodua Community as a result of illegal Chinese mining. Paramount among such environmental security threats include land degradation, water pollution, deforestation, sound pollution or noise, and air pollution.

Land degradation

In an interview with a 1st Inhabitant (traditional ruler in the Awodua community), he pointed out that the illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community in Ghana have led to a drastic deterioration in the value of the biophysical environment of the community. To quote his words he said that

“Most of the Chinese nationals engaged in illegal mining activities at the Awodua community employ the deep shaft mining method where they dig deep down with excavators to reach the earth's crust to be able to locate and unearth gold mineral resources. This method has led to several deep shafts and openings in the area, with little or no regard to reclamation after extraction. Consequently, these openings have death traps for some children, farmers, hunters, farmers, miners, and even some wildlife creatures” (RS 07, 2020).

More so, the 2nd Inhabitant (Assemblyman in the Awodua community), revealed that:

“Most Chinese nationals engage in illegal mining activities in the Awodua community, rely heavily on the use of mercury in their mining activities for preparing minerals. The Mercury amalgamation method is frequently used for preparing gold-bearing minerals since mercury is easily accessible to Chinese excavators. Given this, most Chinese illegal small-scale miners use mercury for extricating the gold. The method essentially includes blending washed metal with mercury” (RS 08, 2020).

The use of mercury employed by some Chinese nationals in the illegal mining activities in the Awodua community has serious harmful consequences for soil fertility to support human life and the biological system. Such a situation contradicts the goals of the EPA in ensuring all human activities carried out in the country do not lead to any form of land degradation. However, from field data, it was revealed by some of the inhabitants that the illegal mining activities by some Chinese in the Awodua community destroy soil fertility to support agricultural activities, hence contributing to food shortages and famine in the community.

Water Pollution

The practice of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community has also had repercussions on the potability and safety of water bodies in the area. Field data by a 3rd inhabitant (a farmer in the Awodua community), revealed that:

The Chinese interest in gold resources in the area, particularly gold has resulted in illegal alluvial mining practices in the area. This has also led to the pollution of major water bodies in the community including river Ankobra, among others. The pollution of the water bodies usually occurs as a result of the release of mercury, metal-rich tailings, and cyanide into streams of major water bodies or catchment territory from illegal small-scale mining activities usually perpetrated by the Chinese in the community. Also, digging exercises and the washing of alluvial gold in the water by some Chinese in the Awodua area have resulted in regular siltation in major streams and rivers in the community where the excavators work. Also, illegal alluvial mining activities by some Chinese on the major streams and river bodies in the Awodua community which mostly involve the use of chemicals and explosive causes the death of fishes and other aquatic organisms, denying citizens of essential nourishment altogether (RS 12, 2020).

As explained by the farmer in the Awodua community the above activities have additionally changed some watercourses of streams and rivers, sometimes denying neighboring communities their major or only source of water, particularly, the Ankobra river. This situation lends credence to the fact that illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana have become hazardous to most water bodies. This is because communities such as the Awodua community which relies predominantly on major rivers and streams for food and employment, which may be contaminated as a result of illegal mining practices by the Chinese, are compelled to desert such sources of water due to environmental security threats which confront them.

According to the medical doctor, in the Awodua community maintaining water which is of good quality is very important for the proper functioning of the environment. However, the Awodua community which does not have an alternative source of water aside from the Ankobra river and other smaller streams is left with no other choice than to continue relying on the contaminated rivers and streams which induce other health and economic security risks. The marginal and poor quality of the river poses a threat to the health of the Awodua community whose inhabitants depend on the Ankobra for domestic activities such as cooking and washing (RS 09, 2020).

Deforestation

Deforestation has also become Ghana's major environmental risk due to the prevalence of illicit mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. This is because most Chinese illegal miners in Ghana also engage in indiscriminate felling of trees to be able to clear lands for their illicit surface mining activities. In an interview with the 4th inhabitant of the Awodua community (i.e., a teacher in the Awodua community), he revealed that:

Vast vegetation cover in the Awodua community is mostly destroyed by the Chinese during their illicit mining activities, with no consideration to safeguarding the fauna or flora during such illegal mining activities. Most, considerable areas of vegetation and land are cleared to make way for illegal surface mining activities by Chinese in the Awodua community, with no regard to ensuring environmental security. This has a significant adverse impact on the land and vegetation, the main sources of livelihood of the people. The deforestation that has resulted from illegal surface mining by some

Chinese miners in the Awodua community has long-term effects even when the soil is replaced and trees are planted after the mining activities. For instance, frequent erosion occurs when surface vegetation is destroyed (RS 11, 2020).

Deforestation due to illegal mining activities by some Chinese miners in the Awodua community has resulted in the deterioration of viable and arable lands for agricultural purposes and loss of habitat for some birds and other animals that perch on trees and other plants. This has culminated in the destruction of the luxuriant biodiversity, vegetation, water bodies, and cultural sites, and water bodies. For instance, a teacher interviewed for the study revealed that “lands and vegetation in most parts of Wassa-Amenfi district including the Awodua community are undergoing fast deterioration in economic value from year to year, mainly due to conspicuous prevalence of illegal mining activities by Chinese in the area.” (RS 11, 2020).

The farmer revealed that agricultural lands are not only generally degraded through deforestation as a result of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community, but the loss of soil fertility for agricultural production has also led to a shortening of the fallow period for efficient farming practices especially in the area. Unfortunately, no consideration is given to embark on afforestation programs by the Chinese who engage in illegal mining activities in the Awodua community. The main motive of these illegal Chinese operators in the area is rather to get the minerals and send them to their home country, with no regard to protecting and preserving Ghana’s environmental security (RS 12, 2020).

Sound Pollution (Noise)

The practice of illicit small-scale mining by some Chinese in the Awodua community also creates excessive noise or boisterous commotion which poses dire hearing challenges to inhabitants and even miners in the community. In an interview with a 5th inhabitant of the Awodua community (a registered small-scale miner in the Awodua community), he pointed out that

The use of the changfang by illicit Chinese miners, for instance, causes loud noise that can affect the hearing abilities of inhabitants and operators in the Awodua community due to the absence of adequate hearing protection. Such activities mostly result in intermittent loud sounds, associated with panics and shocks to residents in areas where such practices take place. This also causes regular palpitation of the heart, hence affecting the well-being of inhabitants (RS 10, 2020).

Illegal mining activities practiced by some Chinese in the Awodua community have rather become annoyance and nuisance to individuals who live in proximity to sites where such operations take place. This is because sometimes such illegal mining activities by the Chinese in the Awodua community cause frightening and regular sleepless nights to residents around mining sites due to the loud noise. Illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community, therefore, do not only have environmental consequences but also pose threats to the personal security of inhabitants in the areas where such activities are practiced. (RS 10, 2020).

Air Pollution

Air Pollution is another drastic environmental security threat posed by illicit Chinese mining activities in the Awodua community, in the Western

region of Ghana. In an interview with a 6th inhabitant in the Awodua community (medical doctor in the Awodua community), he pointed out that:

Air pollution particularly due to illegal mining activities by the Chinese in the Awodua community arises as a result of the emission of mine gases and generation of dust especially during crushing, cutting, blasting, drilling, and pulverizing of the mineral ore. There is a high propensity of air quality deterioration in areas such as the Awodua community due to particles discharged from the sieving of crushed rocks acquired from illegal small-scale mining practiced by the Chinese illegal miner in the area. This often pollutes the air quality, leading to breathing and other eye-related health problems in the area (RS 09, 2020).

It can be deduced from the above that illegal small-scale mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana poses dire health security threats to Ghanaians. This is because such illegal mining activities result in the creation of dust and fumes which pose breathing challenges to inhabitants in areas where such activities take place as witnessed in the Awodua community. The situation can be linked to increased respiratory ailments such as flu and cold (catarrh), as reported by most respondents. It has also been noted that all fine dust at a high level of exposure has the potential to cause respiratory diseases and disorders and can worsen the condition of people with asthma and bronchial stiffness.

Theme 5: The government of Ghana has made significant efforts to curb the prevalence of illegal Chinese mining in Ghana

The fifth theme generated from the interview data revealed that there are efforts by the Government of Ghana in curbing the increasing prevalence of Chinese illegal mining in Ghana. This was shown through 46 coded references from 2045 expressed words in 37 paragraphs. The Respondent from the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana praised the significant role of the media in the fight against illegal miners. He noted that the media which is sometimes considered the Fourth Arm of Government has contributed immensely in influencing the perceptions of Ghanaians, particularly on security issues, with specific reference to environmental security, through conscious sensitization and education about the drastic implications of continuous Chinese illegal mining operations in Ghana. Again he indicated that the media reports on China's interest in Ghana's natural gold resources in particular have made most Ghanaians develop the thoughts that the Chinese Government through its nationals and companies are rather aimed at exploiting Ghana's gold resources for China's self-enrichment or gratification rather than Ghana. He recounted that the media's declaration of war on illegal mining through the formation of the Media Coalition against Galamsey on 4th April 2017 motivated the government to form operation vanguard in 2017. To conclude he cited that this has also resulted in environmental insecurities in Ghana, which has attracted grievances among Ghanaian citizens or dwellers, which could further foster conflicts and tensions between Ghanaians and Chinese and even impair diplomatic relations between Ghana and China (RS 06, 2020).

The official from the Ghana Armed Forces commented that the Government of Ghana in response to the public cry has through the

interagency collaboration between the Ghana Armed Forces (GAF) and the Ghana Police Service (GPS) with other stakeholder institutions taken drastic steps and efforts towards addressing Ghana's environmental security concerns as a result of the illegal activities by predominantly Chinese nationals in the country. He continued that this action go long was to reinforce the determination of the state security apparatuses in promoting and preserving the environment security of the country, which eventually inures to the human security of citizens.

He gave a brief background to Operation Vanguard which was a Military Police Joint Task Force (JTF) formed by the President of Ghana in 2017 to combat the operation of illegal mining in the country. He noted the President H.E. Nana Addo Dankwa-Akufo Addo formed this JTF to operate in the three main regions where the activities of illegal miners were very pervasive, i.e. the Eastern, Ashanti, and Western Region (Currently demarcated into Western Region and Western North)

He indicated that without the collaborative or cooperative efforts between the GAF and GPS with relation to security management to Joint Operations such as 'Operation Vanguard' and 'Operation Halt' to curb illegal mining particularly by the Chinese, Ghana's natural resources such as gold would be greatly exploited by some Chinese nationals in the country. This could pose dire environmental security threats and depletion of the natural environment in most parts of the country beyond salvage. This could have further repercussions on the health and other security areas of citizens. This sends a strong signal to the Chinese Government that Ghana is in no way

ready to compromise its environmental security for bilateral relations and economic development assistance from China (RS 02, 2020).

Theme 6: Several challenges confront Ghana in addressing environmental security threats due to Chinese illegal mining activities in the country.

The sixth theme, generated from the interview data, revealed that challenges are confronting Ghana in addressing environmental security threats due to Chinese illegal mining activities in the country. This was shown through 46 coded references from 2005 expressed words in 36 paragraphs. Despite the above efforts made by Ghana in curbing the pervasive phenomena of illegal mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana, there are a few challenges that confront Government's efforts. Paramount among these challenges include poverty and economic hardships on the part of citizens, financial constraints on the part of Government, Institutional personnel constraints, ineffective/poor collaboration sometimes among the GAF, GPS, and other relevant stakeholders, corruption, and difficulty in obtaining reliable information.

Poverty and economic hardship on the part of inhabitants in the country

The Lecturer from the Institute of Environmental Studies, University of Ghana, has already identified earlier estimates that the current unemployment rate among the youth in Ghana is 48 percent. He revealed:

If the surging youth unemployment rate in Ghana is not urgently and effectively tackled by the government now and becomes worse, most of the youth who find themselves in the unemployed category would resort to all manner of activities (mostly, illegal such as assisting

Chinese nationals engaged in illegal mining activities) for survival (RS 06, 2020).

The above situation according to the lecturer could escalate the already existing environmental security menace such as poor sanitation as witnessed in most parts of the country. Therefore, notwithstanding efforts from the Ghanaian Government, crimes perpetrated by Chinese nationals in Ghana with regards to illegal mining activities will continue to be prevalent in the country if the government does not take austerity measures to address the challenge of harsh economic conditions, extreme poverty, and joblessness which most youths found themselves in. Some of the youth involved in illegal mining are students either in the primary, secondary, and even tertiary institutions. Some are even graduates who know the dire effects of illegal mining on the community but do not care about it. This is because this illegal mining is the source of livelihood and perhaps the only employment opportunity.

Financial Constraints on the Part of the Government

The cost of providing security, including ensuring environmental security is a very expensive business. This is because more equipment and personnel are required to clamp the prevailing or emerging environmental security threats posed by some Chinese nationals in Ghana due to their illegal mining activities in the country. The interview with the official of the Ghana Armed Forces (involved in both Operation Vanguard and Operation Halt to check illegal mining activities across the country), revealed that:

The United States, for instance, uses about \$4 billion to fight the drug world and this is about twenty times what Ghana is expending in its fight against drug trafficking both in the country and in the West

African sub-region. Similarly, tackling environmental security threats posed by some Chinese nationals engaged in illegal mining activities in Ghana requires much revenue to acquire sophisticated surveillance machines and security personnel or intelligence towards addressing the menace (RP 01, 2020).

Though, the GAF and the GPS collaborate, as well as stakeholder institutions such as the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to ensure effective environmental security management, insufficient financial rewards, and benefits for officials of these agencies makes most of them susceptible to bribery and corruption, hence militating against the collaborate efforts to achieve their objective. In addition to the above, governments' revenue and resource challenges towards the course of fighting or addressing internal or domestic environmental security threats posed especially by some Chinese nationals in Ghana is insufficient to meet the changing patterns and trend of such threats in the country. For instance lack of accommodation was a challenge to the task force. Some of the illegal mining took place at night and also on waters. There is the need for the task force to be adequately resourced to fight the menace of illegal mining.

Institutional Personnel Constraints

Management of environmental security threats such as the illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals to safeguard Ghana's natural resources and environment requires a large number of trained or expertise security personnel due to the changing pattern or dynamics of some of the environmental security threats and the modus operandi adopted by the Chinese who perpetrate such illegalities in contemporary times in Ghana. However, in

an interview with an official of the Ghana Armed Forces (involved in both Operation Vanguard and Operation Halt to check illegal mining activities across the country), he revealed that:

The Capacity of the Ghana Police Service as revealed by an official of GAF is a little above 30,000 personnel, whereas that of the GAF is a little 20, 000 personnel. This is not good considering Ghana's population of about 30 million people. This is because per average the ratio of police personnel to citizens at the worst should be 1:3 citizens (RP 01, 2020).

However, considering the personnel capacity of both the GAF and the GPS, even with the best of collaboration that could exist between them to ensure effective environmental security management as seen in Operations Vanguard and Halt, personnel constraint will always be a snag to their efforts. This makes it very difficult for them to carry out the core mandates they are enjoined to effectively clamp the pervasive illicit mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. UN minimum police to population ratio are 1:500. This means that one police officer is to serve five hundred people at a minimum. But the Ghana Police does not meet this ratio, as the population of the Ghana Police Service is around 30,000. Thus with a Ghanaian population of 30 million, the police to population ratio are 1:1200. This means that Ghana is way below the minimum UN ratio already.

Ineffective/Poor collaboration sometimes among the GAF, GPS, and other relevant Stakeholders

Safeguarding Ghana's environmental security goes a long way in contributing to the welfare, health, and productivity of the citizens in the

country. To achieve this goal, Ghana has certain objectives governing the operations of relevant state institutions responsible for promoting and safeguarding Ghana's environmental security. Paramount among such objectives includes conducting investigations into environmental issues; acting in liaison and cooperating with other government agencies, collaborating with foreign and international agencies, as necessary; coordinating the activities of bodies concerned with the technical aspects of the environment to control the generation, treatment, storage, transportation and disposal of industrial waste; issuing environmental permits and pollution abatement notices; making recommendations to the government for the protection of the environment; ensuring compliance with environmental impact assessment procedures; protecting and improving the quality of the environment and security, control and prevention of discharge waste into the environment among several other functions and prescribing standards and guidelines related to the pollution of the air, water, and land.

Notwithstanding the above-stipulated objectives, there are some lapses in some of the institutions in liaising efficiently and effectively cooperating with other government and foreign nationals to help curb incidences such as the prevalent engagement of Chinese in illegal mining activities in the country. As revealed in an interview with an official of the Ghana Armed Forces (involved in both Operation Vanguard and Operation Halt to check illegal mining activities across the country),

The establishment of Operation Vanguard to curb illegal mining across the country, for instance, led to leadership, coordination, and capacity crisis. The roles and responsibilities of the various commanders in the

stabilization tasks were clear on paper but created some challenges on the field. This was because the GAF was authorized by the President to play the lead role in the operation whilst the GPS supports or plays a secondary role, which was somewhat an aberration to domestic or internal security management where the GPS always plays the lead role in cooperation with any other security agency. The immediate change in command of the leadership in Operation Vanguard angered some management and even lower rank personnel of the GPS and this reflected on the field where they did not want to receive any command or directives from the Chain of Command of the GAF in the operation. This resulted in several tensions between personnel of both agencies, some resulting in verbal tensions and attacks (RS 01, 2020).

The above situation attests to the fact that there exists unnecessary competition between agencies. This unnecessary competition could hamper the realization of the goals and objectives of effective inter-agency collaboration. No ship has two captains, such a situation is a recipe for disaster. For smooth command and control, Government must take into account the traditional roles of the GAF, GPS, and other relevant institutions responsible for safeguarding Ghana's environmental security before appointing mission or operation leadership. This will ensure a better structure and flow of command and go a long way to enhance the mandate and objectives of these joint task forces created to clamp down illegal Chinese mining in Ghana.

Corruption

Corruption has been a major snag to effectively addressing environmental security issues or threats due to the illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. In an interview with an official from the Minerals Commission, he identified that:

Due to government's politics coupled with widespread corruption among some state institutions and officials in the country, it sometimes becomes difficult for both GAF and GPS and other stakeholder institutions to collaborate effectively to be able to carry out their mandate of ensuring effective environmental security management amidst the pervasive Chinese illegal mining activities in Ghana (RS 02, 2020).

This is because some top officials of some government and state security institutions in Ghana, sometimes rather give updates to some Chinese engaged in illegal mining activities. Intelligence shared is sometimes leaked to these illegal miners and they thus know every move of these task forces. This means that every action the government takes to clamp them proves futile. This is because instead of providing each other with relevant information to arrest these Chinese engaged in such illicit activities which pose grave threats to Ghana's environmental security, the opposite is done for bribes.

Difficulty in obtaining reliable information

Closely related to the above, the success of stakeholder institutions to effectively address environmental security threats posed by some Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities in Ghana, thrive on informants. However, there is difficulty in obtaining reliable information on the clandestine moves and tactics of these Chinese criminals who engage in illegal

mining in Ghana. In an interview with an official at the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology, and Innovation in Ghana, he revealed that “out of about 100 informants that could be received in a year, only 5 out of them will be genuine or reliable. Also, there is limited in-flow of information” (RS 05, 2020).

Most of the stakeholder institutions, particularly the GAF and the GPS, usually rely on tip-offs from other security agencies before they act, instead of the ability to access first-hand information for their environmental security management processes. This makes it difficult for better interagency collaboration between these institutions in ensuring effective environmental security management in the country, with specific reference to Chinese illegal mining activities across Ghana.

Chapter summary

Some Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities in Ghana has implications for the country’s environmental security. Chapter four showed that there are several conditions present in Ghana that have facilitated the continuous exploitation of Ghana’s gold resources by some Chinese nationals, which have dire implications on Ghana’s environmental security. Some of the major contemporary conditions as identified from field data include among others, corruption, economic hardship, and poverty, institutional inefficiencies and deficiencies, the nature of Ghana’s domestic politics, and Ghana’s quest for accelerated economic growth amidst bilateral economic relations with China.

The study also revealed some dire environmental security threats which bedevil the Awodua Community of the Wassa-Amenfi District, in the

Western region of Ghana due to Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities in the region. Paramount among such environmental security threats include land degradation, water pollution, deforestation, sound pollution or noise, and air pollution.

In addition, despite efforts made by Ghana in curbing the pervasive phenomena of illegal mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana, the study unearthed that there are a few challenges that confront Government's efforts. Paramount among these challenges include poverty and economic hardships on the part of citizens, financial constraints on the part of Government, Institutional personnel constraints, ineffective/poor collaboration sometimes among the GAF, GPS, and other relevant stakeholders, corruption, and difficulty in obtaining reliable information. The next chapter which is the final chapter will therefore provide some plausible recommendations towards addressing the challenges as identified in this Chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory collective case study was to explore the nature and scope of Ghana-Sino relations with a particular focus on the involvement of some Chinese in illegal mining and implications on environmental security in the Wassa-Amenfi District in the Western region of Ghana. The purpose of the study was achieved through purposive interviews of 12 participants who have in-depth knowledge on environmental security threats posed by activities of some Chinese nationals involved in illegal mining in Africa, with a special focus on Ghana. To achieve the purpose of the study, four research questions were developed and guided the study:

1. How have contemporary Ghana-Sino relations facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources?
2. How have illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals influenced Ghana's environmental security?
3. Which challenges have confronted the fight against illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?
4. How can environmental security be improved with specific reference to illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?

To probe the research questions, the study adopted the theoretical framework of the ecological footprint of Mathis Wackernagel developed in 1990. The ecological footprint theory underpinning the study provided insight into the utilization or consumption of natural resources and their associated environmental security consequences to Ghana. The ecological footprint

theory employed by this study highlights the environmental security implications of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana.

The nature of the study is qualitative exploratory. A case study design was used for this study because it facilitated an understanding of the complexity of the single phenomenon of illegal mining activities and its implications on environmental security in Ghana. Data were obtained within 15 days from 12 participants in Awodua. Each of the 12 research participants was asked eight semi-structured open-ended interview questions. Answers were provided, on transcription, resulting in nodes and themes which upon analysis produced rich, thick, qualitative data that addressed the research questions. Chapter five presents the summary and discussion of findings, conclusions, and recommendations on how to address the various challenges that emerged from the study.

Summary of Findings

The findings in chapter four were derived from the study based on analysis of data gathered from interviews; bearing in mind the statement of the problem, research questions, and objectives of the study. The following are summaries of the findings based on the research questions asked.

Findings from document analysis

Secondary data obtained revealed that there has been an influx of Chinese nationals into the mining sector of Ghana. The South China Morning Post, which is a Chinese newspaper, reported in 2013, that an estimated 50,000 miners had left China for Ghana (South China Morning Post, August 23, 2013). Document analysis of this study also found that through the awareness of the media, the country became aware of the dire effects of illegal

Chinese miners in the country. The media in Ghana declared war on illegal mining through the formation of the Media Coalition against Galamsey on 4th April 2017. Typical news report headlines from the media on Chinese illegal mining activities in Ghana include: ‘Operation Vanguard arrests 15 suspected Chinese illegal miners,’ ‘9 Chinese illegal miners arrested as a ban on small-scale mining ends,’ ‘Aisha Huang and four other Chinese illegal miners deported,’ ‘59 Chinese foreign nationals arrested for illegal mining in the Western region,’ among others. Findings established that one of the hindrances that have enhanced illegal Chinese mining in the country is corruption as (Ayee et al, 2011), posited that the canker of corruption has become more pronounced in Ghana’s mining sector as some Chinese nationals who are resident in the country try to subvert government and security personnel and institutions and make most of them become corrupt to be able to engage in illicit mining activities. Secondary data from scholars also established dire environmental security threats in mining towns. Environmental degradation was the order of the day. Bansah et al, (2016), asserted that illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana have become hazardous to most water bodies because the illegal mining activities of these Chinese involve the use of chemicals and explosives. This is a major cause of river water contamination in Ghana.

Findings from interview data

Findings from interview data corroborated findings from document analysis on the influx of Chinese in the illegal mining of Ghana’s gold resources. The findings from primary data showed that Ghana has had foreign (bilateral) relations with China since the 1960s and there was a surge in

Chinese interest in Ghana's gold since the 2008 increase in the global price of gold. Interviews with research participants revealed that China has gained increasing momentum in Africa at the beginning of the Millennium particularly in East Africa, due to the abundance of natural resources in that region. By the end of 2013, it was reported that a significant number of Chinese nationals who were resident in Ghana were engaged in casual and illegal gold mining with the use of Chinese excavators. The situation induced the then President, HE Mr. John Dramani Mahama to establish the state Inter-Ministerial Task Force on 5th May 2013, to address the challenges of small-scale illegal mining activities, particularly carried out by Chinese nationals in Ghana.

Findings from interview data revealed that Ghana has an array of legal frameworks on mining. Article 257(6) of the 1992 Constitution of the Republic of Ghana; reveals that all the minerals in the country are vested in the president who is holding the property in trust for the people of Ghana. The findings also revealed that small-scale mining in Ghana was illegal to citizens until 1989 when the Mining Law 1989 (PNDCL 218) regularized and sanctioned the licensing system to make it lawful for Ghanaian citizens to legally partake in such activities. The Minerals and Mining Act 2006 (Act 703) also makes it possible for miners to register and acquire a maximum of 25 acres for mining activities sanctioned by the Minerals Commission.

Findings from interview data corroborated findings from document analysis on how contemporary challenges in the country have facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources. Primary data identified that there are several conditions present in Ghana that have facilitated the

continuous exploitation of Ghana's gold resources by some Chinese nationals, which have dire implications on the country's environmental security. Some of the major contemporary conditions as identified from field data include among others, corruption, economic hardship, and poverty, institutional inefficiencies and deficiencies, the nature of Ghana's domestic politics, and Ghana's quest for accelerated economic growth amidst bilateral economic relations with China.

Findings from interviews also revealed that illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals affected Ghana's environmental security. Interviews conducted showed some dire environmental security threats which bedevil the Awodua Community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana due to Chinese engagement in illegal mining activities in the region. Paramount among such environmental security threats include land degradation, water pollution, deforestation, sound or noise, and air pollution.

Findings from the interviews again revealed that challenges have confronted Ghana in the fight against illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals. Findings revealed that the Government of Ghana, to some extent, has put in some efforts to clamp down on the prevalence of Chinese engaged in illegal mining activities in Ghana. Despite efforts made by Ghana in curbing the pervasive phenomena of illegal mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana, findings unearthed that there are a few challenges that confront the Government's efforts. Paramount among these challenges include poverty and economic hardships on the part of citizens, financial constraints on the part of Government, Institutional personnel constraints, ineffective/poor collaboration

sometimes among the GAF, GPS, and other relevant stakeholders, corruption, and difficulty in obtaining reliable information.

Findings on the environmental security showed improvement with specific reference to illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana. The findings revealed that the President created “Operation Vanguard and Operation Halt” task forces to combat the operations of illegal mining in the Eastern, Ashanti, and Western regions of Ghana. These joint task forces were effective in the arrest and deportation of some Chinese culprits. This sent a strong signal to the Chinese Government that Ghana is in no way ready to compromise on its environmental security for bilateral relations and economic development assistance from China.

Conclusions

Following the findings obtained from this study, the researcher reached the following conclusions:

Generally, the prevalence of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in Ghana, with particular reference to the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana, has implications for Ghana’s environmental security. Though the Government of Ghana has taken some strides and efforts toward eradicating illegal mining in Ghana, there are still some Chinese nationals and companies who are engaged in illegal mining activities due to prevailing conditions such as corruption, poverty, institutional inefficiencies, among others. Consequently, the rate of environmental crimes and security threats in Ghana continue to be rife, particularly, due to the increasing phenomenon of illegal mining activities by some Chinese residents in Ghana.

Given the above, enforcement of Ghana's environmental and mining laws is the surest way Ghana can effectively deal with or address the pervasive illicit mining activities by some Chinese companies and nationals in Ghana. This will prevent Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources and also safeguard Ghana's environmental security. Stakeholders, therefore, need to be guided by international and national environmental and mining laws to remain focused and proactive in the fight against environmental security menace caused particularly, by some Chinese engagement in illicit mining activities in Ghana. There should, therefore, be proper coordination and dialogue at all levels for formidable action towards curbing illegal mining activities by some Chinese companies and nationals in Ghana, as witnessed in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, in the Western region of Ghana.

Limitations of the Study

This qualitative exploratory collective case study had several limitations that could be considered for future research. Firstly, the study was limited to only one town in the western region which is the Awodua community. The results of this study cannot be generalized as the true experience of the environmental security threat of illegal mining operations of Chinese in Ghana. This is because of the limited number of research participants (12) of which just six were inhabitants of the Awodua Community. The research is an exploratory one that relied on both primary and secondary sources of data. The use of secondary sources of data makes it challenging for the researcher to test the assumptions of the study.

Accessibility to research participants was also a major challenge. The COVID-19 pandemic has made people unreceptive to strangers. This informed

the choice of the number 12 as the sample size for this study. Out of the 12, just six were from the Awodua community. This will not make the findings of this study representative enough as well as the claims of having achieved valid conclusions.

Recommendations

Based on findings from this study, the researcher proposed some key recommendations which include the following:

1. There should be conscious efforts by the Government of Ghana to establish an increased number of sustainable jobs for the youth in the country.
2. Government of Ghana should ensure that state security and environmental protection institutions promote and preserve Ghana's environmental security management across the country through adequate provision of financial resources.
3. Ghana's environmental security management should not mesh with partisan politics. In Ghana, crucial issues are often stymied with the interference of NPP and NDC politics, and this makes it difficult for the fight against illegal mining by the Chinese to be won.
4. Citizens should also become environmental security conscious to appreciate human and national security implications. There are dire environmental security implications of supporting or not reporting criminal environmental security acts such as illegal mining as perpetuated by close friends, relatives, foreigners, and other members of society.

5. Increased funding must also be provided to facilitate research on the prevailing and emerging environmental security threats, with particular reference to Chinese illegal mining activities in Ghana and across Africa.

Suggestions for Future Research

The focus of this qualitative exploratory collective case study research was limited to the Awodua community of the Western region of Ghana. Findings from the opinions of the 12 research participants provided first-hand insights on the environmental security threats posed by illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community. This research study is not exhaustive thus making it imperative for further research on environmental degradation posed by illegal mining activities in other resource-rich communities in Ghana and beyond.

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APPENDIX A

Interview Protocol

The proposed qualitative exploratory collective case study on illegal mining activities by some Chinese at Awodua district and Ghana's environmental security is in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Master of Arts Degree in International Relations and Development by University of Cape Coast (under affiliation arrangement with Nyansapo College), Accra.

The following protocol and interview questions will guide the preparatory process of data collection through to application of semi-structured open-ended interview questions:

1. Ensure certainty of access to research site and participants.
2. Obtain permission to access the proposed research site and participants.
3. Pre-test interview protocol to validate interview questions and recording equipment.
4. Revise/adjust interview questions where necessary.
5. Schedule appointments for the main interview.
6. Prepare and ensure availability of interview tools of audio tape recorder, interview protocol checklist, and note pad.
7. Get to the interview site early enough to avoid being late for scheduled time for the interview.
8. Observe courtesies and protocols of greeting participants including introduction of yourself and purpose for the interview.
9. Show approved formal consent for data collection and for the use of premises to authorities at the research site.

10. Get interviews underway by first starting the digital recorder and then begin from the first question down to the last. Take notes as the interview progress to cross-check key issues raised.
11. To ensure accuracy, summarize main themes to participants and obtain their concurrence.
12. Stop the digital recorder after taking any questions from participants after going through all interview questions.
13. Thank the participant and leave the interview site.

APPENDIX B

Interview Questions

Date:

Time:

Place:

Participant Code:

Position of Participant:

1. How have contemporary Ghana-Sino relations facilitated Chinese exploitation of Ghana's gold resources?
2. Which conditions have contributed to China's exploitation of Ghana's gold resources?
3. How have illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals influenced Ghana's environmental security?
4. Which challenges have confronted the fight against illegal gold mining by some Chinese nationals in Ghana?
5. How do you perceive the extent of cooperation between Ghana and China in promoting environmental security in Ghana amidst some Chinese illegal mining of gold resources in the country?
6. Which environmental security challenges are faced by Awodua district due to the activities of Chinese illegal mining of gold in the area?
7. How can the illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the Awodua community of the Wassa-Amenfi district, be addressed?
8. How can Ghana's environmental security be improved with specific reference to illegal gold mining activities by some Chinese nationals in the country?

Thank you for your cooperation

APPENDIX C

Letter of Introduction

March 1, 2021

Minister/Director

Ministry of Environment, Science and Technology

P. O. Box M232

Accra, Ghana.

Dear Sir,

Request for use of premises – Introduction of Mr. Promise Owusu Yeboah

I write to formally introduce to you the above-named student of Nyansapo College. In partial fulfilment Requirements for the Degree Master of Arts in International Relations and Development (MAIRD), Mr Yeboah proposes to conduct a study into illegal mining and Ghana's environmental security: case study of Awodua, and would appreciate your support in granting him permission and access to the designated site.

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory collective case study is to explore the background of the Ghana-Sino relations, the underlying factors which have contributed to some Chinese nationals' engagement in illegal mining activities in Ghana and also explore the implications of illegal mining activities by some Chinese nationals on the Ghana's environmental security, with specific reference to the Awodua district in the Western region of Ghana. Inhabitants in the Awodua district of Ghana, officials of Minerals Commission and Lands Commission in Ghana, officials of the EPA, research fellow at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, and officials of the

Ghana Armed Forces (involved in Operation Vanguard to check illegal mining activities across the country), will be surveyed in order to share personal experiences on how the activities of some Chinese in illegal mining activities have impacted the environmental security and the development of Ghana. Subjects' confidentiality shall be assured (please Appendix D). Proposed interview questions are attached as Appendix B.

Grateful to have your approval for Mr. Promise Owusu Yeboah to conduct the proposed research results of which shall contribute new knowledge to the world of academia as well as enhance strategies to curb illegal mining activities in Ghana by signing the attached permissions form.

Counting on your cooperation.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Alexander Kwame Archine

/s/ Dr. Alexander Kwame Archine

Mentor (Dissertation Chair)

Nyansapo College

Email: dean@nyansapocollege.edu.gh

Alternative Email: kwamepaintsil@gmail.com

Cell Phone: 0277869765

APPENDIX D

Informed Consent Form

Title of Study

ILLEGAL MINING AND GHANA'S ENVIRONMENTAL SECURITY:
CASE OF CHINESE ACTIVITIES AT AWODUA.

Researcher

My name is Promise Owusu Yeboah and I am a student of Nyansapo College (affiliated to University of Cape Coast) working on a Master of Arts in International Relations and Development. Phone: +233249081677

Email: don.booker9@gmail.com

Purpose of Study

You are being asked to take part in a scientific research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Please ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information.

The purpose of the qualitative exploratory collective case study is to explore in detail Ghana-Sino relations with particular focus on factors accounting for some Chinese nationals' engagement in illegal mining activities and also explore the implications on the Ghana's environmental security. Six inhabitants in the Awodua community, officials of Minerals Commission and Lands Commission in Ghana, officials the EPA and the Ministry of Environment, Science and Technology, research fellow at the Institute of Environment and Sanitation Studies, University of Ghana, officials

at the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation in Ghana, and officials of the Ghana Armed Forces (involved in Operation Vanguard to check illegal mining activities across the country), will be surveyed in order to share personal experiences on how activities of some Chinese in illegal mining activities have impacted the environmental security and the development of Ghana.

Confidentiality

Your responses to this interview will be anonymous. Every effort will be made to preserve your identity and confidentiality of the information you will be providing through the following measures: Alpha numeric code numbers shall be used in place of participant's names. Notes, interview transcriptions, and code numbers identifying participant information will be kept in a file cabinet in the personal possession of the researcher and shall not be made available to third parties beyond authorised officials of Nyansapo College.

Contact Information

If you have questions at any time about this study, or you experience adverse effects as a result of participating in this study, you may contact the researcher whose contact information is provided on the first page. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research participant, or if problems arise which you do not feel you can discuss with the researcher, please contact the College Dean on telephone number 0277869765.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this

study, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be marked “withdrawn” and not be made part of the data for analysis and inclusion in the final report.

Consent

I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

Participant's signature _____ Date _____

Researcher's signature _____ Date _____